

**Validation and impact prediction of
structural variation in wild strains of
*Caenorhabditis elegans***

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this dissertation are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements. This dissertation contains fewer than 20,000 words including appendices, bibliography, footnotes, tables and equations and has fewer than 150 figures.

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Abstract

Caenorhabditis elegans is a commonly used model organism in research on development and human disease. Long-read sequencing technology provides opportunities for studying natural structural changes in DNA content that are potentially responsible for heritable phenotypic polymorphisms among wild *C. elegans* isolates. My collaborator, Cristian Riccio, has gathered PacBio-sequenced genomes of 21 nematode strains and assembled them *de novo*. This new resource facilitated the systematic characterisation of structural variants (SVs) by leveraging split-read and assembly-based variant calling methods. Here, I present the results of the largest survey of common and private structural genomic variation among wild *C. elegans* isolates. To assess the performance of variant discovery, I performed PCR validation of 32 randomly selected SVs that were stratified by the confidence with which they were called across four strains, as well as their presence across other strains. As a first step towards understanding the functional consequences of the SVs, I annotated deletions with predicted functional consequences and their relevance to model human diseases. I was able to identify previously well characterised SVs that have been associated with differences in behavioural and physiological traits among the strains. This implies the potential for this SV list to uncover more functionally important variants. This research is a starting point for the nematode community to collect SVs in natural isotypes, as has been done for SNPs. Through further integration with multi-omics data, the sequences can provide insight into the link between the variation of genetic components and phenotypic diversity. Ultimately, this can accelerate new findings in *C. elegans* biology and support human pathological studies.

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I. Introduction: Scientific background

1.1 The model organism

Caenorhabditis elegans is a small, simple and malleable model organism for studying animal development (Riddle et al., 2011). It has a rapid life cycle of 3 days under optimal conditions, can be frozen for storage and starved to enter a dormant stage and then recover. Moreover, it is inexpensive to maintain and produces large numbers (300-350) of offspring per animal. These self-fertilising hermaphrodites enable genetic studies of inbreeding and crossing with males. By following every cell division within its transparent body, invariant cell lineages have been determined with fully characterised anatomy and development (Sulston et al., 1983).

It is also a powerful tool widely used in biomedical research to find druggable targets to treat for conditions such as Parkinson's disease (Dimitriadi and Hart, 2010), diabetes mellitus and Alzheimer's disease (Morcos and Hutter, 2009). Although pathological phenotypes cannot be observed in *C. elegans*, changes in many gene pathways can, since they are conserved between humans and *C. elegans*. OrthoList surveyed 7663 orthologous genes between worms and humans (Shaye and Greenwald, 2011), which was later updated to 7943 on OrthoList2 (Kim et al., 2018) to support studies on human diseases using *C. elegans*.

C. elegans has a small genome that allowed it to serve as the pilot project for the Human Genome Project, and it was the first multicellular organism to have its entire genome sequenced (Consortium and The *C. elegans* Sequencing Consortium, 1998). The first draft genome of the N2 strain (isolated from Bristol, UK) was produced based on a whole-genome shotgun sequencing strategy, with a genome size of 100 Mb being reported. This assembly then became the reference genome for nematode genome research. The reference genome and other resources are maintained and updated by WormBase (<https://www.wormbase.org>), an international consortium that has existed since 2000. The reference genomes have been collected and constantly improved in this repository.

Sydney Brenner first used the N2 strain of *C. elegans*, which was originally isolated in Bristol, UK, as a model organism to study development in 1974 (Brenner, 1974; Brown, 2003; Sterken et al., 2015). Remarkably, this strain has been used by nearly all *C. elegans* research laboratories. However, wild strains of *C. elegans* have been found worldwide, with strains from different ecological contexts varying phenotypically in developmental timing, longevity, and body size, among other factors (Barriere, 2005). Currently, over 750 wild strains have been collected and profiled to varying degrees (Cook et al., 2017).

In our study, 21 strains of interest have been selected to represent the global divergence of *C. elegans* wild isolates (Figure 1.1) (N2 and CB4856 have been lab domesticated, while the remainder includes wild isolates). The strain relatedness among selected strains is presented in Figure 1.2, which was constructed based on the presence of single nucleotide polymorphisms. From a study (Andersen et al., 2012), CB4856 isolated from Hawaii (USA), DL238 from Manuka (USA), JU775 from Lisbon (Portugal), and QX1211 from San Francisco (USA) were reported as highly diverged wild isotypes. Thus, our collection includes strains that are known to be both highly divergent and conserved relative to the N2 strain.

Figure 1.1: The origins of selected strains (drawn by Cristian Riccio)

Figure 1.2: Strain relatedness based on single nucleotide variant data, pseudo-rooted to the QX1211 strain (adapted from a phylogenetic tree built for 330 isotypes, shared by Erik Andersen. SNPs data can be found on www.elegansvariation.org, (Cook et al., 2017)).

1.2 Structural variants and their impacts

The starting point for mining species variation occurs at the genomic level. (Gaertner and Phillips, 2010) noted that the goal of the *C. elegans* research community has changed from understanding the genetic basis of complex phenotypes to understanding the genetic basis of natural variation in complex phenotypes. They emphasised the use of Mendelian polymorphisms in explaining quantitative traits and the importance of studying natural genetic variation in the nematode population. Although the strains belong to the same species, their DNA content can vary as a result of structural variants (SVs), copy number variations, short insertions and deletions, single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) and variable tandem repeats.

SVs are defined as physical changes in DNA relative to the reference genome that are between 50 bp and 10 kbp in this study. Alkan et al. (2011) define SVs as structural changes >50 bp, here we restrict the size up to 10 kbp because of the read length and accuracy of SV calls that we have (see Appendix 1: Long read assemblies). SVs include genomic

rearrangements such as insertions, deletions, inversions, duplications and translocations. However, while SNPs have commonly been shown as responsible for the disruption or dysregulation of normal gene function and a frequent cause of lethal phenotypes, SVs could also potentially cause similar effects, thereby impacting both gene function and gene regulation. SVs will have a greater potential to impact genetic function due to their larger size and the possibility of altering gene structure, dosage or location.

The impact of SVs has become increasingly evident among the diverse phenotypes of *C. elegans*. There are several known SVs affecting nematode phenotypes. The deletion of the 5th exon in the *glb-5* gene is linked to variation in oxygen sensing among wild isolates of *C. elegans* (McGrath et al. 2009; Persson et al. 2009). Moreover, the loss of copulatory plug formation in certain strains has been related to the insertion of an LTR-Retrotransposon into the *plg-1* gene (Palopoli et al., 2008). Maternal-effect incompatibility between N2 and DL238 can be explained by two structural variants in *sup-35*, leading to the fusion of *sup-35* and the *Y48A6C.1* pseudogene (Ben-David et al. 2017).

CeNDR, a *C. elegans* natural diversity resource (<https://www.elegansvariation.org>) has gathered aligned short-read sequenced genomes for 330 isotypes of this nematode species. The single nucleotide variant data for these wild isolates have been extensively studied. However, SVs have been neglected due to technical limitations, and only small Indels <30 bp are provided by WormBase. A survey of large genomic variation across the global *C. elegans* population will permit a more comprehensive understanding of structural variation and its impacts at the phenotypic level.

With the exception of CB4856, the extent of natural SVs among most wild isolates has not been described. The first attempt to characterise whole-genome structural variation between N2 and CB4856 used array Comparative Genomic Hybridisation (array-CGH) (Maydan et al., 2007). This was performed to deprioritise genes with natural variation for the *C. elegans* Gene Knockout Consortium, which aimed to delete every single worm gene. Thereafter, investigations of copy number variation were performed in 12 *C. elegans* strains (Maydan et al. 2010) using aCGH. Following the introduction of high-throughput sequencing methods, one study profiled genome-wide variation in the Hawaii strain with paired-end Illumina reads

(~100 bp) and single Roche 454 reads (~400 bp) (Vergara et al. 2014). These studies have limited SV length resolution with no defined breakpoint at the base pair resolution. Consequently, knowledge regarding the prevalence and consequence of SVs in wild worm strains remains scarce. Therefore, a systematic survey across the individual genomes is necessary for mapping genomic variation at the functional level in wild isolates.

1.3 Single-Molecule Real-Time sequencing

Today, different sequencing platforms can be combined to determine the genome sequences. One major difference between platforms is the average read length. DNA sequencing technology has been greatly advanced, and third generation sequencers can sequence reads tens of kilobases. PacBio, also known as the Single-Molecule Real-time (SMRT) sequencing method, can sequence long fragments of native DNA and produce continuous reads as long as 60 kb, with an average size of 10 kb (Rhoads and Au, 2015). SMRT cells are used as the sequencing unit, which contains millions of zero-mode waveguides (ZMW). Each DNA template molecule in the SMRTbell libraries will be immobilised to a single ZMW. Sequencing of the circular template is repeated, and the labelled base is incorporated and detected in real-time. Base identity is inferred from the kinetic signatures of this polymerase-catalysed nucleotide incorporation (Eid et al., 2009). Therefore, this requires only one single-stranded DNA, with PCR amplification not being required. Consequently, it can achieve the immediate acquisition of a base signal without amplification bias due to GC contents, with regions previously inaccessible using older sequencing methods now being sequenced. Unfortunately, the PacBio SMRT system has a higher sequencing error rate compared to the Illumina platform. With sufficient genome coverage, errors can be corrected; however, it is not yet accurate enough for single nucleotide variant calling.

PacBio technology has revolutionised methods for resolving genome complexity and structural variant discovery. Although large chromosomal abnormalities can be observed by staining, sub-microscopic SVs are very small and hard to find. Despite the genomes of many wild isolates having been sequenced (Cook et al., 2017), the repetitive regions of these genomes were poorly determined due to short-read sequencing. Compared to short reads,

long reads outperform in unravelling repetitive regions and identifying nested SVs. Thus, PacBio can now characterise these complex regions and power the discovery of structural changes in the nematode genome.

The reference genome has been constantly improved by resequencing and reassembly using increasingly advanced technology. In 2017, a long read-derived assembly of the *C. elegans* reference genome was performed using Nanopore MinION, which is a portable third generation sequencing platform. This has expanded the size of the genome by 2 Mb through the unravelling of repetitive elements (Tyson et al., 2018). This assembly did not have a corresponding annotation file, which makes it hard to be used as the reference genome for genomic studies. A new and more complete genome of an N2-derived strain (VC2010) has recently been assembled (Yoshimura et al., 2019). This genome was shared by our collaborators and was used as the reference genome in our study as it has an annotation file lifted from the WormBase genome. Long-read sequencing has added an additional 1.8 Mb of sequences containing tandem repeat expansions and genomic duplications. In addition, this VC2010 assembly has only 9 contigs and 2 gaps compared to 48 contigs and 42 gaps in the Tyson assembly. Therefore, aligning the wild isolate genomes with this updated genome will reduce false variant calling.

The structural variation of wild strains has not yet been systematically studied due to technological limitations. Since *C. elegans* is also an ideal organism for examining sequencing technology and downstream computational analysis due to its small genome size, the PacBio sequencing of 21 *C. elegans* genomes is presented in this study for the first time as a joint project with Cristian Riccio. SVs can now be predicted with higher confidence; therefore, diversity at the whole genome level can be studied. Nonetheless, these predicted variants must be experimentally validated, while computational analyses of the potential consequences of structural changes in the genome are necessary to provide functional insights.

In summary, a global inspection of unprecedented SVs is critical to establish a thorough understanding of *C. elegans* genome diversification as well as the link between the variation

of genetic components and phenotypic diversity. Sequencing wild isolates will facilitate an improved understanding of the nematode core gene set while also providing a starting point for explaining a fundamental phenomenon: how much variation is tolerated within a species. Additionally, with the variants discovered among these genomes, we can practically take advantage of the natural variation when studying e.g. knockouts of sequence elements. Having full genomes of the wild strains and knowing their SVs will also open up the potential for other people to work on these strains, who are currently restricted to the only choice, N2. In order to achieve this, an experimental validation of the variants is necessary since no gold standards exist for SV calling, and relying on software alone is insufficient with such new technologies. Secondly, the functional impacts of true variants should be predicted computationally, which is required to prioritise the most interesting genomic changes, such as severe mutations that can be studied first. This project contributes to Cristian's work, which aimed to characterise the heterogeneity of *C. elegans* species at the genomic level.

II. Discovery and experimental validation of SVs

2.1 Introduction

Two variant calling algorithms, Assemblytics (Nattestad and Schatz 2016) and Sniffles (Sedlazeck et al. 2018), have been specifically developed for long-read sequencing and were applied in the present study by Cristian Riccio. Distinguishing between computational errors and true variants is a central task for assessing the reliability of the SVs revealed here by PacBio sequencing and the variant callers. Visualisation of the physical existence and alignment of variants by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and the Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV) can provide evidence for the evaluation of SV discovery performance. In order to validate the SVs cost-effectively, a stratification strategy can group variants based on their quality to guide PCR experiments. Since 21 nematode strains are studied here, common and private variants in the population also permit the reconsideration of their evolutionary distance.

2.1.1 Variant calling methods

There are four conventional methods to computationally identify SVs with whole-genome sequencing data, as depicted in Figure 2.1. These include 1. The read depth method, which can detect duplications and deletions using evidence based on the unexpected distribution of read counts; 2. The read pair approach, which evaluates the concordance of pair-ended reads, such that variant calling is supported by the inconsistent mapping and orientation of read pairs; 3. The split-read method, which can align different sections of a read to the reference and scan for gaps or stretches in the read; and 4. The assembly-based method, in which contigs are first built from the reads and variants are called from gaps in aligning the contig against the reference genome (Tattini et al., 2015). These strategies were employed in the human 1000 genome project, which used short-read sequencing for cataloguing human genomic variation (Mills et al., 2011). With third generation sequencing, these methods remain applicable, except long read length replaces the need for read pair sequencing. As such, the split-read-based and assembly-based approaches can be greatly advanced since the

long reads can directly span structural events and greatly improve the genome assembly of individual strains. Thus, in the present study, we applied both methods to our collection of SMRT-sequenced genomic data.

Figure 2.1: SV signatures and patterns (A Deletion, B Insertion, C Inversion and D tandem duplication. RC = Read Count, RP = Read Pair, SR = Split Read, AS = Assembly. Source: Tattini et al., 2015).

The first variant caller we applied was Assemblytics, which is a web tool for SV detection in long-read assembly (<http://assemblytics.com>, Nattestad and Schatz, 2016). The NUCmer program of the aligner MUMmer (Kurtz et al., 2004) can rapidly align each sequence contig to the entire genome and SVs are subsequently called by Assmblytics (Figure 2.2.a). A unique-length filtering step then occurs to select for alignments anchored in a significant amount of unique sequences. For instance, repetitive sequences are removed since they do not contain unique anchoring alignments, which thereby avoids false variant calling. This software permits SV discovery from high-quality genome assemblies, which we obtained for 20 wild isolates of our species of interest (except for strain CX11262). For each contig,

Assemblytics analyses the presence and type of spaces between each consecutive alignment pair of a contig and the reference. Assemblytics can detect genomic variants between 1 bp -10 kbp, namely insertion, deletion, tandem contraction and expansion, repeat contraction and expansion. Sequences within each alignment pair are also scanned to check for minor variations. These single-nucleotide variants and small variants were not included in the analysis since we only aimed to study large SVs.

The second variant caller is split-read-based. Sniffles (Sedlazeck et al., 2018) can detect complex structural variations in reads aligned by the long-read aligner NGMLR and minimap2 (NGMLR was used as recommended in the protocol). Long reads are first split into non-overlapping 256 bp sub-reads and mapped independently to the reference genome. Co-linear sub-reads are then grouped together and realigned to the reference (Figure 2.2.b). NGMLR utilises a convex gap-scoring model to facilitate the alignment of high-error long reads against the reference genome, where longer alignments become proportionally less costly. The highest scoring non-overlapping combination of aligned segments for each read is then selected by NGMLR. These alignments are subsequently scanned by Sniffles for SV calling. Breakpoints are grouped into clusters that are then filtered before outputting the results. Sniffles can detect insertion, deletion, inversion and duplication as the standard types, based on evidence from split-reads, intra-alignment gaps, high-mismatch regions and read depth. Therefore, SVs are filtered based on their size, position, type and coverage so that false variants are removed.

Figure 2.2.a: Schematic pre-processing and alignment for variant identification with Assemblytics.

Figure 2.2.b: Schematic pre-processing and alignment for variant identification with Sniffles.

2.1.2 Studying and validating SVs

The integration of SVs in a population is feasible through another tool known as Survivor (Jeffares et al., 2017). This tool allows a multi-sample variant call format (VCF) file to be obtained through merging individual VCF files across the samples. The default merging parameter is 1000 bp, which implies that reported variants that are within 1 kbp could be the same variant called by Sniffles multiple times, thus repeated variants are filtered and shared variants across individuals are merged together. From the combined VCF files, variants that passed filtering could be grouped and mapped back to the individual variant files to keep only unique variant calls for downstream analysis.

Since we have a collection of N2-related and N2-distal strains as well as a large number of loci throughout the genome, strain relationship can be inferred from this combined data. The population variant file reports a binary code containing characters 1 or 0 for the presence and absence of each variant across the strains, respectively. From this binary data, the binary SV alignment of wild strains against each other can be the input for IQ-TREE (Nguyen et al., 2015), which is an efficient phylogenetic software that infers an SV tree and facilitates the reconstruction of the strain relationship, i.e. modelling the likely SV tree using maximum likelihood (ML) estimation. A model is fitted from a sequence alignment with the best-fit model automatically selected by ModelFinder (Kalyaanamoorthy et al., 2017). Evidence of the phylogenetic groups in ML-based trees can be found via the ultrafast bootstrap (UFBoot) approximation approach (Chernomor and Von Haeseler, 2017). UFBoot can calculate unbiased branch supports by running a random subset of the data multiple times for the phylogenetic analysis. Branch support values are reported as the percentage of bootstrap replicates in which the node is observed.

One important question to be answered is how much confidence we have in identifying true SVs. Variant discovery using PacBio reads is a relatively new area of research and there is not yet an established bioinformatic pipeline. As such, it is crucial to assess the performance of the variant callers. Only insertions and deletions (INDELs) are defined in the same way by these two variant callers and can thus be directly compared. The use of multiple variant callers will generate a consistent group of INDELs that are shared by this software; however,

this only addresses the consistency among software. Statistical consideration is required to determine the precision, sensitivity and specificity of these two approaches. Ideally, a collection of known SVs should be used to test the overall performance of this software by their ability to recall these variants. Despite the aforementioned points, there are a few well-characterised SVs; however, the number is too small to provide statistical power. Thus, it is not possible to benchmark these two variant callers in this manner due to a lack of sufficient ground truth SVs. In other words, no useful *C. elegans* SV database is publicly available for each strain due to the past technical limitations of SV discovery. Although this study cannot benchmark software, it can create a novel SV resource to support future functional studies on important SVs.

The principal validation approach for variant calling is to utilise PCR to amplify the genomic fragments and gel electrophoresis to experimentally visualise the presence and the size of predicted SVs. Before performing PCR, called variants can be stratified into confidence groups based on computational analysis, such that a relatively high confidence group of SVs is expected to be fully verified as true SVs in PCR experiments. In order to achieve this stratification, the criteria for a reliable SV should be defined and specific parameter for each criterion should be weighted sensibly. For example, SVs that are called in common by variant callers and have good coverage should be assigned into the high confidence group. A random forest model would be ideal for this stratification, though this cannot be adopted due to the lack of confirmed SVs that can be used to train the model. Instead, different weightings of quality parameters can be tested. The stratified groups of the test runs can be checked, such that those SVs with high coverage with well-characterised breakpoints called by both variant callers are classified in the high confidence group. This consensus equation can calculate quality scores for SVs in each strain, which is then used for SV stratification.

Visually checking alignments is an essential component of genomic analysis. Directly checking read mapping can provide evidence independent from variant calling, as one can discriminate variant calling errors from sequencing errors. IGV (Robinson et al., 2011) enables the interactive and integrative visualisation of read mapping to the reference genome alongside annotated genomic features. It also supports the flexible loading of our local reference genome, VC2010 (Yoshimura et al., 2019), as previously described. In this case,

checking the alignment information of PCR candidates in IGV allows for the prediction of PCR outcomes and cross-comparisons of common and private variants in the population.

2.2 Methods and Materials

2.2.1 PacBio sequencing and genome assembly

C. elegans has a hermaphroditic lifestyle and thus low heterozygosity in its genome. We further reduced heterozygosity by sequencing genomic DNA extracted from a population that started as one individual on a Nematode Growth Media plate. The strains used in this work are listed in Table 2.1. Cristian Riccio extracted high molecular weight (HMW) DNA from 20 of the 21 studied strains (except for JU751, which was extracted by me) using the QIAGEN Genra Puregene Tissue Kit for HMW DNA purification. PacBio Sequel v2.0 and v2.1 sequencing chemistry were used with Template Prep Kit v1.0 (done by the Sanger Institute sequencing facility). Cristian assembled the SMRT-sequenced genome *de novo* with Canu 1.8. *De novo* assembly was achieved by overlapping long and contiguous DNA fragments in the absence of the reference genome. The assemblies with Illumina reads were polished using pilon 1.23 and the contaminated bacterial reads were removed from bacterial diets by Cristian.

In summary, the quality of long reads and assemblies are ideal for downstream analysis. These quality metrics can be found in Appendix 1: Long read assemblies. Since our genomic data have good quality, I expected that SVs in N2 would be marginal and that CB4856 would be frequent, as known from the literature.

EA strain	SX strain	City of Origin	Country of Origin
AB1	SX3368	Adelaide	Australia
CX11262	SX3384	Los Angeles	USA
CB4856	SX3292	Hawaii	USA
DL200	SX3351	Addisababa	Ethiopia
DL238	SX3367	Manuka	USA
ECA248	SX3305	Paloalto	USA
ECA36	SX3306	Auckland	New Zealand
EG4725	SX3304	Amares	Portugal
EG4946	SX3286	Salt Lake City	USA
JT11398	SX3303	Lake Forest Park	USA
JU394	SX3302	Hermanville	France
JU751	SX3341	Perreux	France
JU775	SX3298	Lisbon	Portugal
LKC34	SX3295	Madagascar	Madagascar
MY23	SX3296	Roxel	Germany
N2	SX3254	Bristol	UK
PB306	SX3350	Southampton	UK
PS2025	SX3287	Altadena	USA
QX1211	SX3356	San Francisco	USA
QX1791	SX3383	Ulupalakua	USA
GXW1	SX3399	Wuhan	China

Table 2.1: Strain list. EA strain names are recorded by the Anderson lab on <https://www.elegansvariation.org/strain/global-strain-map/>. SX strain names are given by the Miska lab as descendants of the EA strain. City of Origin and Country of Origin are where the strain is found and collected. ECA248 has an alternative name, known as CB4855.

2.2.2 Variant calling

The reference genome (VC2010) FASTA file was shared by our collaborator (Yoshimura et al., 2019), while the WormBase reference N2 genome was downloaded from WormBase (version WS270). Cristian performed long-read alignment against both references with NGMLR (0.2.7): “ngmlr -r reference -q reads -o output.sam --presets PacBio” and contig alignment against VC2010 with Nucmer (3.23): “nucmer -maxmatch --minmatch 100 --mincluster 500 reference decontaminated.reads -prefix”. The following options were specified by Cristian for running Assemblytics “Assemblytics input.aln anchor 10,000”. He also performed “sniffles --report_seq --mapped_reads aligned.aln -vcf raw.vcf --genotype -n -1” for running Sniffles (1.0.11). Furthermore, he shared the vcf outputs from Sniffles and tab delimited outputs from Assemblytics with me.

Sniffles has an automatic filter in the output using parameters by default. The minimum number of reads that support an SV is 10, the maximum number of split segments a read is aligned at before being ignored is 7 and the minimum mapping quality of alignment to be considered is 20. The default unique contig sequence anchor of Assemblytics is 10 kbp.

2.2.3 Processing variants

The filtering of Sniffles raw reads and merging the individual variant vcf files involved one step using Survivor 1.0.6: “SURVIVOR merge combined_vcf_files.txt 1000 1 1 -1 -1 -1”, which was run by Cristian.

I then ran a bioinformatic analysis on the individual Sniffles and Assemblytics and combined Sniffle files in R studios version 1.1.463, while graphical summaries were drawn using the ggplot2 R package. For reproducible, scalable and parallel data processing, I used Snakemake as the workflow management system where a Python script ‘Snakefile’ was written to run a series of commands to obtain the required outputs with specified software.

I wrote Perl scripts to draw the Circos representation of the SV genomic distribution using Circos (Krzywinski et al., 2009) to enumerate the structural features and spatial

characteristics across all five autosomes and chromosome X of each strain. A bin size of 10 kbp was used in plotting and the highest peak in each track was found to give the scale of the histograms.

2.2.4 Stratification methods

Since Assemblytics does not report any quality measure of SV, it is hard to inspect the quality of the variant output. Thus, the only useful information for guiding a PCR validation experiment on predicted groups of variants at different confidence levels is to add more confidence for calls shared with Sniffles. Thus, the stratification step focused on all filtered Sniffles variant calls, which were artificially split into low and high confidence groups. This grouping was achieved through calculating a ranking score based on a combination of quality parameters that included read counts, the standard deviations of the breaking points (STD_quant_Start and STD_quant_End) and the parameter for representing the shared calls.

Shared calls among the variant callers can be defined at several levels:

1. Location-wise, though no exactly matched coordinates were observed across the datasets.
2. Checking if variants in approximate locations are the same. The determination of approximate variants was achieved by overlapping the coordinates using the GRanges function in R. Overlapping variants can be assigned as identical length-wise if the variants are within 25% of the size difference (see Appendix 2: Length similarity) or content-wise, i.e. if the detected variants have the same DNA sequences. This can be assessed by aligning the sequences reported by both software.

Before alignment, SV sequences must be gathered. However, Assemblytics does not output the actual sequence of the variant. Since the regions between alignments are scanned by Assemblytics, there are essentially two coordinate systems in the assembly-based method: one for the contig and one for the reference. This means that start and end points on both the reference and the contig are required to specify the SV loci. Thus, sequences on both the reference and the contig must be extracted to represent the true variant identity. Regarding overlapping SVs among the variant callers, it would be ideal to align the Sniffles sequence with the Assemblytics contig sequence and the Assemblytics reference sequence. However, pairwise alignment scores are much easier to calculate and interpret than multiple sequence

alignments. Therefore, I simplified the Assemblytics output by using only the larger sequence, i.e. I used a contig sequence to represent an Assemblytics insertion and a reference sequence to represent an Assemblytics deletion. While Sniffles reports sequence information for the variant, it only reports the sequence from the read best representing the variant.

For deletions, fetching sequences from the reference genome with specified coordinates and comparing them is straightforward since the reference sequence is well-defined and can be directly aligned. However, this is not the case for insertions since the Sniffles output only reports one representative inserted sequence. This is further complicated by long-read sequencing being error-prone at the base calling level (13-15% on www.pacb.com). As such, only when assembling enough reads can errors be corrected. Therefore, the reported sequence cannot be treated as the true variant sequence. Thus, the local assembly of aligned reads is necessary to generate a consensus sequence that can subsequently be compared to the Assemblytics insertion represented within a single contig sequence. This requires a *de novo* assembly of the locally aligned reads; however, the local assembly of aligned reads at putative loci is problematic since there is currently no functioning tool to address it (see Chapter IV). Consequently, no ideal pairwise sequence alignments can be performed for insertions. Thus, I have generated alignment scores for deletions but used length similarity for insertions as the quality scores for the shared group of variants.

A sequence pair can be aligned either globally or locally, with the former approach aligning the query and the subject end to end while the latter finds the best-aligned region of the subject to the query. The major difference between these approaches is that there can never be negative scores in local alignments. Since only the two ends vary for deletions, alignments are at the centre of the sequence pair. Longer variants have more matches and more complex sequences aligned, resulting in higher scores that move them to the top of the ranked table. Moreover, since these variants are more influential, assigning these with higher scores is desired. Thus, local alignments were calculated for a sequence pair that were similar in size and extracted based on variant coordinates provided by Sniffles and Assemblytics. The table was sorted and ranked, followed by splitting the total variants table into two groups, where higher scores were in the high confidence group and lower scores were in the low confidence group.

In the Sniffles output, ZMW and read value (RE) both measure the level of sequencing evidence, where ZMW value is the number of PacBio sequencing wells that support the SV and RE is the number of reads that support the variant. If $RE:ZMW = 2$, the templates are sequenced twice. Most sequenced templates were single-pass in this study, i.e. $RE:ZMW = 1$. Only read value was used in the stratification procedure to avoid overweighting the sequencing depth of each locus.

To enable the ranking of SVs based on their likelihood of being a true variant, I normalised the scores for each parameter by dividing by the maximum value. I also tested various weightings of the parameters and checked split groups between different combinations of settings until the desired high and low confidence groups were obtained.

The final equation used in calculating the scores for ranking was $a*3+b*c*3-d$, where:

- a = Normalised alignment scores /length similarity
- b = Normalised read counts
- c = Normalised STD_quant_Start
- d = Normalised STD_quant_End

Here, evidence from the other variant caller and breakpoint statistics were the most important measures; only a and c were weighted more, though d was not since variants with a well-characterised start point are also likely to have a well-characterised end point.

With the ranking scores calculated, I split each SV type into two confidence groups for each strain. The stratification groups of the randomly selected SVs with the raw quality data can be observed from Table 2.2.

ID	Parent Strain	Type	Confidence group	Reads	Alignment score	Length Similarity	Start SD	Stop SD
1	CB4856	Deletion	High	92	925.47791	0.98	1.390965	3.110291
2	CB4856	Deletion	High	115	374.55124	1	0.592349	0.439298
3	CB4856	Deletion	Low	14	NA	NA	26.853305	28.946502
4	CB4856	Deletion	Low	31	NA	NA	1.549193	10.65833
5	JU394	Deletion	High	53	166.46744	1	0	0.27735

6	JU394	Deletion	High	125	120.88715	1	0.283981	0.553581
7	JU394	Deletion	Low	45	NA	NA	13.731185	15.138752
8	JU394	Deletion	Low	28	NA	NA	10.488088	6.88684
9	MY23	Deletion	High	43	377.30655	1	0	0.218218
10	MY23	Deletion	High	42	341.37259	1	0	0.534522
11	MY23	Deletion	Low	11	NA	NA	2.12132	3.507136
12	MY23	Deletion	Low	20	NA	NA	8.97775	9.643651
13	EG4946	Deletion	High	87	NA	NA	0	1.21042
14	EG4946	Deletion	High	71	126.83243	1	0	0
15	EG4946	Deletion	Low	14	NA	NA	7.300685	14.310835
16	EG4946	Deletion	Low	14	NA	NA	0.447214	1.048809
17	CB4856	Insertion	High	49	NA	1.04	4.330127	6.221602
18	CB4856	Insertion	High	68	NA	-1	0.618347	4.003675
19	CB4856	Insertion	Low	24	NA	-1	0.5	138.976317
20	CB4856	Insertion	Low	16	NA	-1	1	47.069098
21	JU394	Insertion	High	81	NA	-1	18.811566	0.490909
22	JU394	Insertion	High	119	NA	0.996	0.390567	3.167633
23	JU394	Insertion	Low	48	NA	-1	15.91383	17.932745
24	JU394	Insertion	Low	16	NA	-1	24.066574	35.948574
25	MY23	Insertion	High	30	NA	-1	0	2.569047
26	MY23	Insertion	High	32	NA	1.02	0	1.198958
27	MY23	Insertion	Low	37	NA	-1	35.442442	33.485486
28	MY23	Insertion	Low	24	NA	-1	3.122499	44.017042
29	EG4946	Insertion	High	51	NA	-1	4.849742	10.581115
30	EG4946	Insertion	High	98	NA	1.02	0	12.301485
31	EG4946	Insertion	Low	27	NA	-1	2.401922	3.100868
32	EG4946	Insertion	Low	16	NA	-1	3.535534	43.176382

Table 2.2: Stratification of pseudo-randomly selected SVs. Their quality metrics, including number of reads, local alignment scores (for deletions if overlapping with Assemblytics results), length similarity (for INDELs if overlapping with Assemblytics results), standard deviations for start and end breakpoints are shown.

To obtain deletion sequences, I extracted coordinates from the Sniffles and Assemblytics files, respectively. I then used the `fastaFromBed` from `bedtools v2.16.2` command to output the variant sequence specifically for Assemblytics deletion: “`fastaFromBed -fi input.ref -bed input.bed -fo output -tab -name`”, using reference coordinate pairs mapped to the reference genome. I also used the `getfasta` function from `bedtools` to extract sequences 500 bp upstream and downstream of the variant in the reference genome for primer design. The `sample` function in R was used in random selection of the strains and candidate variants, while the `set.seed()` function was used to reproduce the number from a sequence of pseudorandom numbers (I used `set.seed(123456)` or `set.seed(12345)`). Thus, if re-run with the same `set.seed` number, this selection will be reproducible.

2.2.5 PCR

For the technical validation of SVs, I performed PCR assays on 32 randomly chosen variant candidates with specific sets of primers spanning predicted breakpoint junctions. For each strain, two insertions and two deletions were pseudo-randomly selected from both the high confidence and low confidence groups of the filtered and ranked SV list for each individual strain. In total, this equals to:

$2 \text{ SVs} * 2 \text{ SVTYPES} * 2 \text{ confidence levels} * 4 \text{ strains} = 32 \text{ PCRs}$.

Although I started by randomly selecting two candidates from each confidence group, these did not always have appropriate primers designed on Primer-BLAST. This is likely because SVs often reside in repetitive regions, while the rate of undesignable candidates was indeed high. For deletions, this only worked when I randomly selected 12 candidates; out of these 12, only 2 could have primers designed. This was true for the four strains that I randomly selected. For insertions, this procedure worked for six candidates from each confidence group of each strain.

Since the primer pairs could theoretically work on all of the genomes, I also checked the validity of putative INDELs for other natural isolates in addition to the strains that were pseudo-randomly selected. For each selected INDEL candidate, its presence across the population was checked in the population metadata. Since I only had genomic DNA for 18 strains remaining after sequencing, three of the strains were not validated. Therefore, I

checked the predicted presence and genomic range of the variant of interest in all 18 strains. In certain cases, I also extracted strain-specific sizes of the same variant from the metadata.

I designed primers in the flanking regions of the computationally identified SVs (within 500 bp upstream or downstream of the SV) on Primer-BLAST by NCBI using the default settings (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/tools/primer-blast/>), and I ordered dry DNA oligos from Sigma Aldrich (<https://www.sigmaaldrich.com>). The primer pairs are listed in Table 2.3.

ID	Strain	T	G	C	Start	End	L	F Oligo	Forward Primer	R Oligo	Reverse Primer	N	V	Y	Z
1	CB4856	D	High	II	12531647	12532120	473	M10953	CGAGAAACCATCAG GACTGGAG	M10954	GGAGAGTGCTAG CTGTTGT	846	373	11	7
2	CB4856	D	High	III	6852335	6852526	191	M10955	GGGGCAAAATGAC AGGGACA	M10956	CCCGAGAGTTGC ACTGGAAG	608	417	1	17
3	CB4856	D	Low	IV	2398489	2401139	2650	M10957	ATCGGAACTCTGC TCGGCAC	M10958	GACTTCGGGACA CAAGTCCG	3183	533	1	17
4	CB4856	D	Low	V	695127	695368	241	M10959	ATCGCTTCACCAAT TGTTGTCA	M10960	GTCCAGTATCCCG AGCAGTTAT	1028	787	9	9
5	JU394	D	High	IV	17125781	17125865	84	M10961	GTTCCCAGCTCTCT TGCCAAA	M10962	TTGTACACCCGGTG GTCAICTG	459	375	3	15
6	JU394	D	High	V	1659915	1659977	62	M10963	TGCCAAGAACAAG CAATGCG	M10964	TGTCAGCCGACTT TACATGC	425	363	1	17
7	JU394	D	Low	IV	2280535	2280670	135	M10965	ACGCTTACTTACC ACCACAAA	M10966	CGTTGTAACGCAT TAGCGCA	656	521	8	10
8	JU394	D	Low	IV	1028927	1029453	526	M10967	AGTGTCTGTAGTG TGCAACCAA	M10968	CAGTTCCTGGAA GAAGCGGG	1112	586	6	12
9	MY23	D	High	II	8945555	8945702	147	M10969	GGTAGACGACCAC CAAGCTG	M10970	TCAAAGACAAAG CAACCACG	618	471	11	7
10	MY23	D	High	X	14239613	14239746	133	M10971	AGGATGTCTAGGT CGGCCAT	M10972	GCTGTTTTTGTGT GGCTGGT	266	133	4	14
11	MY23	D	Low	I	14554552	14554608	56	M10973	TCGGAGGGCTTGT TCTATCG	M10974	AATCCCAACTTCC AGACGGG	362	306	1	17
12	MY23	D	Low	III	12832024	12832299	275	M10975	GCTTCGGGTTTTTC ACCGAAC	M10976	AGTCGTTTCTCC TCTGCCG	902	627	9	9
13	EG4946	D	High	X	7669181	7669251	70	M10977	CGAAATGACAAGC CGTGACC	M10978	TGACTTTTCTCCTC CCGCCTC	513	443	10	8

14	EG4946	D	High	X	16275731	16275795	64	M10979	AATGGGGGAGCCA ACTAAGA	M10980	AGGAGCCAGACA GACGTTCA	433	369	5	13
15	EG4946	D	Low	II	2199769	2199900	131	M10981	CTGGGTTTGGCAT GTTTCAGTG	M10982	TGGTGCTAGATG CTCAAGGTG	692	561	6	12
16	EG4946	D	Low	V	18536178	18538262	2084	M10983	AAGACCATCGGGC TGTGATAC	M10984	TACTCGGCGTGC GTAATTGA	2542	458	4	14
17	CB4856	I	High	II	12419157	12419261	109	M10995	AAGAAATCCGACGA CGCACTG	M10996	GTAATGTTACGGC GCCACAC	931	1040	16	2
18	CB4856	I	High	V	1789691	1789836	147	M10997	CTCCAAGGCGTGT TGAACAGA	M10998	AATCTAAAATGGG CAGGGGGA	649	796	10	8
19	CB4856	I	Low	V	3367099	3367526	472	M10999	CCGATCGTAGCGA GAGTGAC	M11000	TTTGGCTAATTTCC GTGGCCT	1013	1485	1	17
20	CB4856	I	Low	III	3745132	3745250	123	M11001	AGCCCATGAGTTG GTTTTCTCT	M11002	TCGTGGTAGGCA CGTAGAAT	382	505	10	8
21	JU394	I	High	III	459657	460051	375	M11033	GAGAACTTGTGTTG CGCAGTG	M11034	CGTTCCACGAAG GTGCTACT	785	1160	16	2
22	JU394	I	High	IV	3674082	3674207	130	M11007	GAAGTCACAGTCG ACACCGT	M11008	GAGACGCTGAGA ATCTGGGG	307	437	11	7
23	JU394	I	Low	IV	2064887	2065053	199	M11009	AACAGACCCGGTCC AAAGTCC	M11010	CACGCITCTTGTA CGCAACC	317	516	9	9
23.2	JU394	I	Low	IV	2064887	2065053	199	M11035	TAGTCCGTAGTCC ACGATCCA	M11036	AGCTTCTCAGAG AGCGACCTA	423	622	9	9
24	JU394	I	Low	X	16967642	16967741	79	M11011	CAATAGGCACACTGG GAGGGGA	M11012	CTGCCAGGTTTCA CATCGAC	557	636	11	7
25	MY23	I	High	V	16842398	16842471	77	M11013	AAAGGATGCTGTG TTTTGGCAC	M11014	TACGGGGGATCTG AAAAATCGGG	685	762	5	13
26	MY23	I	High	X	7599876	7599933	60	M11015	AGTGACAGACATT TCCGCGT	M11016	CGTGGCATTATTC GACACTCG	495	555	12	6

27	MY23	I	Low	V	17626281	17626372	70	M11017	CCAGGGCAAAAAGG CCTAGAA	M11018	CTCAGTTGGCACT GGCAAAAG	599	669	2	16
28	MY23	I	Low	V	16845713	16846028	286	M11019	TCCGCCTAATTAC AGCCAGC	M11020	AGTTACAGCGGG AATCGCAT	967	1253	1	17
29	EG4946	I	High	III	12312973	12313788	816	M11025	TTCCATAGAGGCG TTAACCTCA	M11026	TGGAACGTCCTTT TCCACACT	1082	1898	9	9
30	EG4946	I	High	X	10949912	10950343	462	M11027	ACACACGGTCTCT TGCCAC	M11028	TCAACACACCCCC CGCAATAA	631	1093	16	2
31	EG4946	I	Low	III	1525998	1526164	171	M11029	AGCTGGCTGGAAA TCCCTTCAA	M11030	CCAATAGTTTTGG AGCAGTGCG	823	994	6	12
32	EG4946	I	Low	V	2988199	2988327	105	M11031	CTCCTCGCGGTGTG ATGTAGT	M11032	GGCGACTCTGAT GGGGATAG	354	459	6	12

Table 2.3: Primer pairs for PCR amplification of 32 selected candidates. T: Type (D = Deletion, I = Insertion), G: Confidence Group (High or Low), C: Chromosome, Start: start coordinate of the SV, End: end coordinate of the SV, L: Length (bp), F & R oligo: oligo ordering ID for Forward and Reverse primers recorded by the Miska lab, Forward and Reverse Primer: primer sequences, N: predicted size of PCR product for N2 (control)-like strains, V: predicted size of PCR products for strains with the variant, Y: number of strains predicted having the SV among the 18 strains tested here, Z: number of strains predicted without the SV among the 18 strains tested here.

The candidate SVs were PCR amplified using the same genomic DNA prepared for whole-genome sequencing. All reactions were run with no attempt to optimise PCR conditions. I used Q5 High-fidelity DNA polymerase (New England, M0491L) and 100 ng of gDNA as a template in a 50 µl reaction volume containing 1X Q5 Reaction Buffer, 200 µM dNTPs, 0.5 µM forward primer and 0.5 µM reverse primer, 0.02 U/µl Q5 polymerase and nuclease-free water. I ran all reactions with annealing temperatures predicted by the Q5-specific Tm calculator (<https://tmcalculator.neb.com/#!/main>). Thermocycling conditions for a routine PCR in each step are shown in Table 2.4:

Step	Temperature	Time
Initial Denaturation	98°C	30 seconds
32 Cycles	98°C	10 seconds
	*50-72°C (based on Tm calculator)	15 seconds
	72°C	20-30 seconds/kb
Final Extension	72°C	2 minutes
Hold	4°C	

Table 2.4: PCR thermocycling conditions for Q5 DNA polymerase

I ran gel electrophoresis of the PCR products on 1.75%-2% TAE agarose gel with ethidium bromide (150 V, 400 mA, 30 mins, Bioline HyperLadder 100 bp and 1 kbp) and imaged with Bio-Rad Gel Doc XR + image lab software. Two sizes of DNA ladder (100 bp or 1 kbp) were used according to the size of the SV candidates. Validity was assessed based on the size of bands on DNA electrophoresis gels. All band sizes were relative to the N2 band size, which was the control. The template for the gel layout is provided in Figure 2.3.

Example for a DEL randomly selected in strain X

Figure 2.3: Schematic gel layout template. In addition to the selected SV in this example, there are five other strains also contain this variant based on population evidence. Since it is a deletion, the true positive bands are lower compared to the reference.

An evaluation of the performance of variant calling was achieved by measuring the validation rate of predicted variant presence and putative size on agarose gels. Since no ‘gold standard’ variant set exists, the sensitivity, specificity and precision of the entire SV list existing in a genome cannot be properly determined. However, the relative performance of variant prediction by Sniffles can be estimated from true positive and false positive rates of the PCR experiments. Here, I define these performance measures for Sniffles hits specifically given the ground truth as determined by the gel readouts. As given in Table 2.5: Positive/negative refers to variant calling, true/false refers to gel evidence. Thus, true positive (TP) means a variant is captured by Sniffles and has been experimentally validated. True negative (TN) means there is no variant of interest called in the locus and the band size is the same as the reference. False positive (FP) refers to a called variant with no evidence of a gel band of the expected size. False negative (FN) is when Sniffles does not call a variant, though a variant does exist based on gel observation.

	Called by Sniffles	Not called by Sniffles
Gel readout - True	TP	FN
Gel readout - False	FP	TN

Table 2.5: Definition of PCR validation results.

- Sensitivity is defined as the percentage of the target true positives that were predicted as true positives $[TP/(TP+ FN)]$.
- Specificity is defined as the percentage of the target true negatives that were predicted as true negatives $[TN/(TN + FP)]$.
- Precision is defined as the percentage of the predicted true positives that were validated as true positives $[TP/(TP + FP)]$.
- Accuracy is defined as the percentage of predictions that were validated as true $[(TP + TN)/(TP + FP + TN + FN)]$.
- The false positive rate is calculated as $[FP/FP+TN]$.

For diagnostic performance measurement, I used Prop.test in R for one-sample proportions tests without continuity correction where the null probability is 0.5. Confidence intervals were calculated as the exact 95% binomial confidence interval for performance measurements.

2.2.6 IGV

IGV version 2.4.16 was used. Before loading in IGV, reads-reference alignment bam files were generated (as described in 2.2.2) and contigs were aligned to reference bam files created by Cristian using 'bwa mem -E0.5 -x intractg reference contig'. I then used SAMtools to sort and index these files, which could then be recognised by IGV. The annotation files were shared by our collaborator (Erich Schwarz). The confirmation of SV alignments or evidence for false PCR results were gathered as IGV screenshots.

2.2.7 Studying strain relatedness with SV data

I transformed the binary code from the combined population variant file to run IQ-TREE 1.6.11 with "iqtree -s test.fa -bb 1000". Then, I used the UFBoot contree file constructed by

IQ-TREE was used to draw an SV dendrogram. The R ‘dendextend’ package (Galili, 2015) allowed me to perform a visual comparison of the different dendrograms based on SVs and SNPs.

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Structural variant metrics

Assessing complex structural events is part of the evaluation process for our collection of *de novo* assemblies using SMRT-sequenced long reads. Regarding the N2 strain we used in this study, our assembly is of high quality since very few variants were detected by both Sniffles and Assemblytics. In other words, the sequence identity of this N2 assembly and the VC2010 reference genome is highly similar since VC2010 is very close to N2. (This number is smaller than the SV number of VC2010 called with the standard N2 reference genome (Yoshimura et al., 2019).) Moreover, while there was also a VC2010 reference assembly made with Nanopore sequencing (Tyson et al., 2018), the quality is not guaranteed; thus, I compared our results to the standard N2 reference genome. Here, over 30,000 variants were detected that affected 21 strains, with some divergent strains having thousands of variants and more N2-like strains having much less, as shown below.

2.3.1.1 Sniffles outputs

The size distribution of Sniffles raw counts for inversions, insertions, duplications and deletions in 21 strains can be seen in Figure 2.4. The sum of counts in each type are 7105, 48090, 10535 and 50241, respectively. INDELs are more common than duplications and inversions. Among the wild isolates, there is a general trend that the SV size distribution is very skewed, with shorter SVs being more frequent than longer SVs. This is expected since larger changes are less likely to be frequent as they are less likely to occur in the first place, as they bring more severe consequences for the genome and are more difficult to tolerate. As evident in Figure 2.4, N2 has the least number of variants predicted since the reference genome VC2010 is a modern strain derived from N2. CB4856 is a well-known divergent strain which has previously demonstrated high SV numbers (Vergara et al., 2014). Moreover, strains ECA36 and QX1211 are shown to carry the largest number of deletions and insertions; after filtering, the total number of INDELs for these strains are 8798 and 8744, respectively.

Figure 2.4: Size distribution of Sniffles outputs (5000 bins) for 21 strains. SVs within 50 bp-10 kbp. INV=inversion, INS=insertion, DUP=duplication, DEL=deletion. Each strain is represented by a panel.

After filtering unreliable variants and merging shared variants across the strains using Survivor, the total counts of unique SVs are 2147, 10236, 3319 and 14015 for inversions, insertions, duplications and deletions, respectively. Figure 2.5 compares INDEL counts before and after filtering. The median retention rates for deletions and insertions are 90.2% and 81%, respectively (9.8% filtered for deletions and 19.0% filtered for insertions).

Figure 2.5: INDEL counts before and after filtering with Survivor.

A filtered variant (CB4856) is shown in Figure 2.6, where a 1.7 kbp deletion was reported twice. After filtering, the variant with a lower allele frequency, i.e. the fraction of reads supporting the SV (0.34) was removed by Survivor.

A)

	CHROM	POS	END	SVLEN	AF
	chrII	All	All	All	All
1765	chrII	305837	305902	65	0.588235
1766	chrII	318975	320718	1743	0.34
1767	chrII	319820	321549	1729	0.8

B)

1765	chrII	305837	305902	65	0.588235
1767	chrII	319820	321549	1729	0.800000

Figure 2.6: An example of filtered results for a deletion A) before filtering and B) after filtering.

However, even after filtering and merging SVs within 1 kbp using Survivor, some variants remained unfiltered. This is evident in the case of N2, where a variant was called five times in the same loci at the end of chromosome I; after filtering, it was reduced to two calls. However, the remaining ones were identical. This was at the end of chromosome I, which is a very complex region and thus difficult for SV analysis. The default 1 kbp can be changed, which requires further investigations on the appropriate distance to filter our repeated calls while conserving real calls.

The Circos plots (Figure 2.7) represent the SV distribution of the four SV types along each of the five autosomes and the X chromosome across 21 strains. Variants were distributed differently along each chromosome for each strain. For example, EG4946 and JU394 have a similar number of total variants (1483 vs 2657). Chromosome IV is very conserved in EG4946 relative to N2, whereas JU394 has many SVs located on this chromosome, as shown in Figure 2.8. A previous study of chromosome IV revealed that there are two broad regions of piRNA clusters where the piRNA precursors are transcribed from, with over 15000 21U-RNAs being expressed (Batista et al., 2008). Further investigations of this region could provide insight into regulatory differences among these two strains.

Figure 2.7: Circos plot showing SV distribution for 21 strains. Left: variants called with the new VC2010 assembly, right: variants called with the WormBase N2 reference. The size of the highest peak in each track was determined to give the scale of histograms. Each strain has six blocks (5 autosomes + X chromosome).

Figure 2.8: Chromosomal distribution of SVs in EG4946 (red/left) and JU394 (yellow/right), y-axis: position along the chromosome (Mb). Drawn with the R package chromPlot.

Figure 2.9 presents the percentage of total variants against the number of strains sharing the variant(s). This distribution is left-skewed, i.e., nearly 38% of the total variant counts are private to a specific strain. The number decreases rapidly for variants shared by more than one strain. Overall, there are 9 variants (4 insertions and 5 deletions) that are present in all of the 21 studied strains (see Appendix 4: Regions that are likely to be unique to VC2010), which could imply specific changes in VC2010, such as lab adaptations and/or missing sequences in the reference genome.

Figure 2.9: The proportion of total variants shared by a specific number of strains.

In aggregate, filtered INDELS could potentially affect a few megabases of genomic sequences. The affected length of each strain is presented in Figure 2.10. Compared to ubiquitous SNPs in the genome, SVs are long and more profound since they affect around 0.64% (insertion median) to 1.5% (deletion median) of the total genome size of *C. elegans*. Although there are roughly the same number of insertions and deletions (see Figure 2.5), the results suggest that deletions are longer for all strains.

Figure 2.10: Total sequence length affected by Sniffles INDELs.

2.3.1.2 Assemblytics outputs

The Assemblytics SV distribution plot (Figure 2.11) shows a pattern similar to the skewed distribution of the Sniffles output (Figure 2.4). However, the total counts are much fewer, with only 13855 and 11221 for insertions and deletions, respectively. QX1211 and ECA36 have also been identified as having a higher density of SVs occupying their genomes. The total length of sequence affected by SVs as predicted by Assemblytics is presented in Figure 2.12. Notably, the total inserted length is generally larger than a deletion—a result that is the reverse of the Sniffles output. The total length is much shorter compared to the Sniffles plot (Figure 2.10).

Figure 2.11: Size distribution of Assemblytics outputs (5000 bins) for 21 strains. SVs within 50 bp-10 kbp. Each strain is represented by a panel.

Figure 2.12: Total sequence length affected by Assemblytics INDELS.

2.3.1.3 Integration of SV outputs from Sniffles and Assemblytics

I integrated SV calling results by Sniffles and Assemblytics, and the shared calls are presented in Figure 2.13. The shared calls accounted for only a small proportion of the total calls. QX1791 and GXW1 have shown a second pattern where Assemblytics called relatively more variants compared to other strains.

Figure 2.13: Compare INDELs reported by Assemblytics and Sniffles. Blue: only reported by Sniffles, green: shared calls reported by both variant callers (overlapping and having similar length), red: only reported by Assemblytics.

For a closer investigation of the shared group, I also calculated the proportion of shared calls over the total variant counts, where the Jaccard index was calculated as $\text{Percentage} = (\text{Shared} / (\text{Sniffles-only} + \text{Shared} + \text{Assemblytics-only})) * 100\%$. The results are presented in Figure 2.14, where only three strains shared $\sim 30\%$ of the total deletions for each wild isolate. The median overlapping rate was 21.7% for deletion and 25.9% for insertion called by both software. This implies that Assemblytics and Sniffles, which are run using different variant calling principles, only agreed on a small proportion of variants based on the location and size of SVs in the *C. elegans* genome.

Figure 2.14: The percentage of total variants shared by Sniffles and Assemblytics.

2.3.2 VC2010 reference genome vs WormBase reference genome

I compared outputs from Sniffles given the different reference genomes. The WormBase reference genome is the N2 reference from the WormBase website, whereas the VC2010 reference genome is the newer and more complete genome sequenced using long reads (Yoshimura et al., 2019). Any change in the variant number is due to sequence differences in the reference genomes. The distribution of the variants across the six chromosomes of each strain is highly variable, as seen in the Circos plot (Figure 2.7). These two plots were created

using type-selected, size-selected and filtered variant datasets. The general pattern of divergence among the wild population was conserved between variants called with the WormBase genome and with the newer VC2010 assembly. Variants (against the VC2010 reference) were more clustered at the chromosome arms compared to the centre when we zoomed in at the chromosome level (Figure 2.15), which has previously been observed when studying the WormBase reference genome (Andersen et al., 2012).

Figure 2.15: The distribution of all CB4856 variants (Sniffles) across each chromosome.

I only compared the variant counts and did not overlap Sniffles outputs by coordinates with the WormBase and VC2010 reference, as I did previously for Assemblytics and Sniffles outputs with the VC2010 reference. This was not feasible here due to different reference genomes being used in variant calling with the WormBase and VC2010 references using Sniffles. New sequences were added to the new VC2010 assembly, which implies that a variant could be shifted to nearby regions in the VC2010 reference relative to the WormBase reference.

Total count numbers for comparing the two reference genomes are visualised in Figure 2.16. The general pattern suggests more deletions and fewer insertions in VC2010 datasets compared to WormBase datasets, with the exception of strain GXW1. There were 1.7 Mb of new sequences added to the new reference genome (Yoshimura et al., 2019), which could have resulted in some old insertions being mapped and thus disappearing; on the other hand, the appearance of new deletions can be explained by some new sequences not existing in the wild strains. There is likely a trade-off between the number of deletions and insertions regarding the addition of new sequences. This is only a hypothesis based on the innate differences between the Sanger-sequenced WormBase N2 and PacBio-sequenced VC2010 assemblies. No matter which reference is used, the relative abundance of each SV type is consistent, with the exception of one strain (GXW1) that remains unclear.

Figure 2.16: Differences in variant number using the WormBase N2 reference genome and the newer VC2010 reference assembly.

2.3.3 Evidence from PCR validation and IGV inspection

2.3.3.1 Overall results

Four strains (CB4856, JU394, MY23 and EG4946) were pseudo-randomly chosen from the 21 strains studied. I performed experimental validation on 32 loci by PCR and gel electrophoresis. SV candidates covered loci on all chromosomes with sizes ranging from 60 bp to 2650 bp. Since only 18 strains had genomic DNA remaining after being sent for SMRT sequencing, 576 candidate SVs (32 PCR reactions * 18 strains) were tested. I tested all of the natural isolates—with apparent and no apparent INDELS—within the PCR amplicon. All agarose gel photographs with their specified ID numbers and gel layouts with specified strain names have been included in Appendix 3: Gel images.

In summary, 9 PCRs had all lanes with bands present, while 18 PCRs had a total of 60 lanes missing. Missing lanes could be due to a variety of factors: 1. extension of INDEL length into the primer regions and incorrect locus prediction by the variant caller; or 2. the presence of other SVs in the strain-specific genome. Since all primers were designed against the reference genome, there could be differences in the primer region between the reference and the wild strains which prevented PCR amplification. For example, a deletion could be even larger than predicted, resulting in the primer regions also being deleted and thus the primers failing to anneal. Another explanation is that there are other variants present in the primer loci that are not complementary to the predicted primer pairs, which could be due to an insertion, multiple SNPs, or, most commonly, a deletion resulting in no sequence being present at the genomic locus and available for primer binding.

Overall, four PCR reactions failed due to various reasons: ID 3 amplified multiple regions, as evidenced by the presence of multi-bands; ID 16 failed as the reference control had no band (likely to be an experimental error, I could not rerun as I run out of the control genomic DNA); Some lanes had a smeared gel and off-targets in ID 21; and PCR ID 31 was the only PCR that failed completely, i.e. gel with no band presence, which implies poor primer quality as it did not anneal to any strain (These 4 cases should be repeated with improved

experimental design). In total, PCRs of 60+86 candidates failed as evidenced by empty lanes, smearing, multi-bands or off-targets in the gels.

Three additional PCR amplifications failed for the randomly selected target that was stratified (to clarify, not all candidates in these PCRs failed, but rather the third lane—the stratified target of interest—failed). Thus, for the 32 targets in the stratified groups, seven SVs were unsuccessful at the PCR stage, of which are three deletions and four insertions. By checking individual contig-reference alignment files, these are most likely due to primer annealing failure. All high confidence group variants, both insertions and deletions, were validated. For the 16 deletions, 13 were successfully amplified, with both high and low confidence group SVs being validated. Within this group, ID 15, which was a low confidence deletion with only 14 reads, was still verified. This demonstrates that the coverage requirement is not high for SV discovery using Sniffles. Regarding the 16 insertions, 12 were successfully amplified. Although there were 3 false positives for the stratified variants, I classified them as low confidence insertions, and their alignment files were assessed as being weak in IGV prior to running the PCR. In total, for the 32 candidates randomly selected among the 4 strains, the validation rates were $22/25 = 88\%$ and 100% for the high confidence group ($32-7 = 25$, 3 FPs, thus $25-3/25$).

For PCR reactions among the population, a total of 148 out of the 576 candidate targets were verified as bona fide variants; therefore, 148 were TPs. Furthermore, 252 were TNs, 26 were FPs, 4 were FNs. Regarding the variant calling performance for insertions and deletions, insertions had a lower accuracy rate than deletions. The breakdown of the scores is presented in Table 2.6. In summary, among the variants called by Sniffles between 50 bp and 10 kbp with a depth >10 reads, the accuracy of deletion discovery was 98.1%-100% for deletions present on the gels and 81.8%-91.6% for insertions (95% CI). The false positive rate was 0-2.7% for deletion and 13%-25.8% for insertion (95% CI). Deletion candidates had no FP or FN results, which results in sensitivity and specificity values of 100% under the assumption that the validation experiments are all accurate and have sampled randomly within the genome (although ID 16 may contain FN results see Appendix 3: Gel images). However, Sniffles may have missed many regions, as evident from variants only being discovered by Assemblytics. This suggests that selected candidates may be imbalanced and undersampled.

		Sensitivity			Specificity			Precision			Accuracy		
		TP	FN	TN	FP	Mean	95% CI	Mean	95% CI	Mean	95% CI	Mean	95% CI
Deletions		65	0	138	0	1	94.4%-100%	1	97.3%-100%	1	94.4%-100%	1	98.1%-100%
Insertions		83	4	114	26	95.40%	88.8%-98.2%	81.40%	74.2%-87.0%	76.1%	67.3%-83.2%	86.8%	81.8%-90.6%

Table 2.6: Variant calling performance measurements. TP: True Positive, FN: False Negative, TN: True Negative, FP: False Positive, CI: Confidence Interval.

2.3.3.2 Experimental evidence

There were several successful and unsuccessful gels worthy of more detailed analysis (Lane identities for all gels are shown in Appendix 3: Gel images.). In Figure 2.17.a, Gel 8 is an exemplar gel for a deletion, with 100% band presence and 100% accuracy in size prediction. Moreover, the IGV alignment evidence (Figure 2.17.b) is strong for the six strains with this deletion. In Figure 2.18, Gel 17 displays an insertion with accurate prediction for all 16 strains with this SV; here, the band size also agreed very well with the predicted size.

Figure 2.17.a: Gel for SV ID 8 (deletion).

Figure 2.17.b: An IGV browser screen snapshot (chromosome IV: 1028800-1029600) of alignment evidence for SV ID 8 in 6 strains (In order: JU394, ECA36, MY23, QX1211, QX1791 and GXW1). Black lines represent deletions within the reads. Reference genome is the VC2010 assembly. Pink and blue reads are aligned to the forward and reverse strand respectively. Mismatched positions are highlighted in the coverage tracks.

Figure 2.18: Gel image for ID 17 (insertion) with predicted size (bp) of each band by Sniffles labelled.

There were also several failed PCR reactions. For ID 4 (Figure 2.19), only four lanes have bands present (including the N2 reference); however, it was predicted that nine strains should show a deletion of 241 bp. I checked the primer alignments with the wild strain contigs against the VC2010 genome, and the reverse primer had no alignment. In other words, this means no sequence existing in the strain-specific contig and thus the failure of the PCR reaction.

Figure 2.19: Gel image for ID 4 (deletion), only 4 strains were successfully amplified.

On the other hand, Sniffles could potentially mislocalise variants, miscall variants and ignore real variants. Figure 2.20 (ID 23) is an interesting case in which Sniffles reported the incorrect start and end locations. The first PCR attempt did not identify this insertion given

the PCR range chrIV 2064873-2065189. Checking alignments around the FPs allowed inspections on mistarget potentials as a result of mislocalisation by Sniffles. The first gel of ID 23 indicated inaccurate variant prediction. As seen in the IGV screenshots presented in Figure 2.20.a, the reported breakpoints were incorrect and IGV alignment evidence provided the more likely locus of this variant. Thus, I redesigned the primer pairs with new coordinates (PCR range chrIV: 2064506-2064928) that were very close to the reported one. The presence of this insertion is confirmed with the redesigned primers at the bottom of the gel presented in Figure 2.20.b. Notably, the validated bands are counted as true positive in the statistical calculations above.

Figure 2.20.a: IGV evidence (chromosome IV: 2,064,666-2,065,088) for ID 23 insertion in JU394. Blue arrow points to the reported SV location by Sniffles and black arrow points to the correct region as validated by the second round of PCR. Reference genome is the VC2010 assembly. Pink and blue reads are aligned to the forward and reverse strand respectively. Insertions with annotated size are shown by purple blocks within the reads.

Figure 2.20.b: Top, gel image of the first PCR attempt for ID 23; bottom, gel evidence for validated ID23 with a redesigned primer pair. Deletion was validated on the second attempt.

In Figure 2.21, ECA36, JU751 and QX1211 represent FNs since they presented an insertion band but were not called by Sniffles as insertions. Notably, Lane CX11262 and QX1791 also included deletions. However, I did not consider these as false negatives since the verified size of this variant demonstrated that Sniffles was correct regarding the absence of an insertion.

100bp N2 MY23 DL200 ABI EG4725 ECA36 CB4856 JU394 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 EG4946 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1

Figure 2.21: Gel image for of ID 28 (insertion). There are both insertions and deletions.

The three aforementioned stratified FPs were in the low confidence group. They were identified through an indifferent band from the reference in the third lane of gel IDs 20, 22 and 32. Their IGV evidence was very weak (see IGV screenshot in Figure 2.22.a & Figure 2.22.b) compared to candidates with strong alignment evidence (Figure 2.17.b). In gel ID 24 (Figure 2.23.a), JU394 was predicted to be in the low confidence group and the IGV screenshot for JU394 was very weak (Figure 2.23.b). Since I checked the alignments before PCR, the failure did not come as a surprise. The bottom track of Figure 2.23.b is the true

positive JT11398, which contained more supportive reads. These false positive results emphasise the need for manually checking the read alignments for variant of interest.

Figure 2.22.a: Weak IGV evidence (chromosome III: 3,745,105-3,745,223) for insertion ID 20 in strain CB4856, as only very few reads have the insertion. Reference genome is the VC2010 assembly. Insertions with annotated size are shown by purple blocks within the reads. Pink and blue reads are aligned to the forward and reverse strand respectively.

Figure 2.22.b: Weak IGV evidence (chromosome V: 2,988,046-2,988,735) for insertion ID 32 in strain EG4946, as only very few reads have the insertion. Reference genome is the VC2010 assembly. Insertions with annotated size are shown by purple blocks within the reads. Pink and blue reads are aligned to the forward and reverse strand respectively.

100bp N2 JU394 DL200 ECA36 CB4856 JT11398 DL238 JU751 EG4946 QX1211 QX1791 GXWI AB1 EG4725 CX11262 LKC34 MY23 PB306

Figure 2.23.a: Gel image for ID 24 (Insertion).

Figure 2.23.b: IGV screenshot (chromosome X: 16,967,608-16,967,654) for insertion ID 24 in strain JU394 (above) and JT11398 (below) long read alignments against the vc2010 reference genome. Insertions in the reads are shown by the purple blocks, which are scattered in this region. There are more insertions in the reads of JT11398 compared to JU394.

Three samples (QX1211, AB1 and JU394) are missing from SV ID 1 (Figure 2.24). I checked the contig-reference genome alignment in IGV to troubleshoot the underlying reason for PCR failure. The results indicate that the primer regions were missing in the individual genome; therefore, primers could not bind and amplify the targeted sequence. One interesting feature observed from Figure 2.24 is the presence of two types of deletion bands: CB4856, DL238, EG4725, LKC34, GXW1, JT11398 and DL200 have slightly higher bands than JU751, PB306, MY23 and CX11262. By extracting this variant (ID 4471) from the population variant table; indeed, two types of deletion were reported with exactly the same pattern as previously described (on chromosome II, the former: 12531647-12532120; the latter: 12531504-12531973). This further demonstrates the power of accurate variant calling for deletion in this study.

Figure 2.24: Gel image for ID I (Deletion).

2.3.4 Studying strain relatedness with SVs

The relatedness of wild isolates could be estimated from the presence and absence of SVs in worm genomes. Since many variants are found in the multiple isolates, these loci were used as markers to refine the phylogenetic relationship. I was able to build a relationship tree, which is presented in Figure 2.25. GTR2+FO+R2, a general time-reversible model for binary data, was selected as the best-fit model. Bootstrap support percentage values from ML with 1000 bootstrap replicates are provided above the internal branches at each node. Bootstrap support values can be interpreted as to what extent a branch may exist in the real data. These values indicate the proportion of the same branch that were observed when repeating the tree reconstruction by sampling on a set of data with replacement. For instance, a value of 100 implies that the node appeared in all replicates and is thus well-supported. This SV tree differed from the tree that was built for 330 worm isotypes based on single nucleotide variants in the population (Tree shared by Erik Andersen, SNPs data can be found on www.elegansvariation.org, (Cook et al., 2017)). I selected our strains of interest from this large tree and compared the results with those of the SV tree.

Figure 2.25: SV tree with branch support bootstrap values, showing strain relatedness on the basis of SV presence.

A tanglegram was created for a visualisation of this comparison. Two dendrograms were plotted side by side facing each other with the same labels connected by lines in Figure 2.26. Both have been pseudo-rooted to QX1211, which was applied in the original SNP tree. I coloured the branches to highlight the common sub-trees present in both dendrograms. The entanglement score of the best alignment layout was calculated as 0.0078. Thus, when aligning the trees to the best of my ability, the overall topologies of each tree (outlined as bold edges in the dendrograms) are different. In other words, strain relatedness inferred from SNPs and SVs is very similar but not identical based on the tree shape of calculated genetic distances. Both trees placed ECA36 as the most divergent from the other wild isolates. The SV numbers used here for tree generation are different from the SNP number (SVs (24251) in 21 strains vs SNPs in 330 isotypes). When comparing the SNP tree and the SV tree, bootstrap values of the SNP tree is also essential to evaluate the most likely representation of the branch layouts. This SV tree may provide new insights into complex strain relationships, e.g. JT11398 and DL200 being more closely related based on SNP data, but not as close based on the SV tree. Nonetheless, comparing the branch support values of this branch in both SNP and SV tree is necessary to confirm the true relatedness of these two strains.

Figure 2.26: A tangrogram for comparing strain relatedness inferred from different variation data. Left = SV dendrogram, right = SNP dendrogram. QX1211 (at the top) was used as the outgroup in rooting both dendrograms. Topological structures of both trees were highlighted in bold. Common sub-trees were coloured. Entanglement is kept at minimum and is shown as connected lines. Drawn with the R package dendextend (Galili 2015).

2.4 Discussion

Our collection of wild *C. elegans* isolates demonstrated a high level of divergence based on SV polymorphisms across the genomes. The split-read and assembly-based variant calling approaches enabled us to detect and resolve a variety of genomic structural features with our long-read whole-genome sequencing data. Previously, (Che, 2016) applied Sniffles and Assemblytics to two PacBio-sequenced human genomes. The Jaccard index values for Sniffles and Assemblytics were 6.2% and 6.5% for insertions and 18.2% and 18.4% for deletions, respectively. With the limited validation numbers in our study, it remains difficult to speculate why Sniffles and Assemblytics again yield different results. However, there are several possibilities: 1. they are based on different principles; 2. the input quality matters; and 3. the parameter settings are not optimised, *etc.*

Most variants are private to a specific strain, which suggests ongoing independent events in different strains across the world. For variants shared between 21 strains but not the reference, this could imply highly conserved DNA sequences not represented by the reference (i.e. shared long insertion may implicate absent sequences in the reference genome that are not yet captured by current sequencing technology or the recent adaptation of the lab domesticated reference strain). It is thus crucial to continue tracking changes that are occurring in the reference background to avoid reference errors that further complicates analysis.

By definition, the reference genome should be representative of the wild population. Often, a reference is used to quickly assemble new genomes and does not necessarily contain all gene sets in every individual, which represents a well-known but not well-addressed problem. Ongoing studies on human reference genomes are an illustration of this. The Genome Reference Consortium human genome (build 37) was sequenced from a DNA mixture of 13 donors and is essentially a mosaic of their genomes (Editorial, 2010). This widely used genome still misses 300 Mb DNA for African descendants and this finding has added extra contigs to the human reference genome (Sherman et al., 2019). The 1000 Genomes Project

sequenced 1000 genomes from 26 human populations with the aim of building a global reference for human genetic variation (1000 Genomes Project Consortium et al., 2015).

For *C. elegans*, the N2 reference was also a mixture of N2 individuals from multiple labs (although all descendants from one individual were chosen by Brenner) (Sterken et al., 2015). Despite it only containing genes unique to N2, this reference has long been a standard since most studies involve N2. Currently, an increasing number of investigations are using highly divergent strains for which N2 is not as representative. Although most sequences are conserved, there are highly variable regions. For N2-distant strains, mapping to divergent strain references such as CB4856 may aid in the study of phylogenetically underrepresented strains. Thus, instead of using N2 alone or a population-averaged genome, multiple reference genomes with annotated variation for each population will potentially be available for each strain in the future as the cost of sequencing is reduced.

Gathering more high-quality genome assemblies of the wild isolates is an important contribution to building the *C. elegans* pangenome. This will make it possible to identify the core gene set shared by most strains and variable gene sets present in only certain strains. In short, genomic research is now applying PacBio long-read sequencing in numerous efforts to characterise structural variation that is largely missed by short-read sequencing while also building population-specific reference genomes.

In this study, I focused only on local INDELS of a 50 bp-10 kbp putative length since they can be reliably determined based on the average read length. However, longer SVs exist and can have profound impacts, e.g. compatibility between N2 and CB4856 can be explained by a 19kb deletion in *zeel-1* (Seidel et al., 2008). This variant was called in the CB4856 datasets (length 21885/20025, called twice), but was ignored in the present study due to the large size (beyond what can be reliably identified based on the long read length). In particular, 1813 INDELS are larger than this boundary and are excluded from the combined and filtered population metadata, of which 499 have lengths reported as 999999999. Sniffles could not resolve the size (again the reads are not long enough to determine the length of these insertions) and 630 are between 10,000 bp and 50,000 bp. I ignored duplications (3993 in the combined data) and inversions (2772), which also indicate large genomic events. Moreover, I

did not investigate long-range intra- or interchromosomal rearrangements, such as translocations (2150), which are often complex structural changes that have widespread impacts in the genome. Furthermore, inverted duplications (INVDUP) are another interesting variant type, and Sniffles also reported cases where it was uncertain about the SV type (e.g. DEL/INV), which requires manual checks for individual cases (these are not reported in the combined population data). Therefore, longer and more complex variants await investigation.

While the overall performance of Sniffles variant calling is quite promising, there are several limitations to the validation procedure that I used in this study. First, the sampling of SVs was not truly random in R and the selection of PCR candidates was restricted by the practicality of primer design. Second, the PCR design should be improved to reduce the rate of missing lanes. When designing primers for targeted candidates, one should use the genome sequence of the target DNA, not that of the reference genome. This is especially true for studying SVs since they often reside in complex regions and cautions must be taken when amplifying these regions. The missing lanes in current experiments can be as well targeted for optimization. Moreover, only band sizes were compared here, with size estimation being rough and relative. Validation accuracy can be improved by Sanger sequencing the PCR products. These improvements would be non-trivial but laborious, a better automated procedure may be devised. Alternatively, to facilitate future studies for SVs, data simulation can serve as a powerful and cost-effective alternative for benchmarking these variant detection algorithms without the laborious generation of a ground truth set. The performance of Sniffles on human variant calling has been assessed using this heuristic method *in silico* (Sedlazeck et al., 2018) and can be repeated with *C. elegans*. Performance assessment by simulation requires the simulator to be capable of generating test data with all of the important features of real data, such as bias in SMRT sequencing and the specific properties of the nematode genome.

Variants only called by Assemblytics were not experimentally examined in this study. It is difficult to add quality measures for aligning contigs, unlike for aligning multiple long reads, since statistical measurements can be taken for a number of reads. On the other hand, Assemblytics can theoretically report accurate insertion sequences since contigs are used instead of multiple erroneous long reads. By checking the alignment evidence in IGV, there were variants that had not been reported by Sniffles. Therefore, more potential SVs remain to

be discovered by Sniffles. To aim for a complete and reliable set of SVs, different computational approaches should be combined since called variants may have remarkable differences in terms of the genomic regions discovered, size range and breakpoint precision. Combining multiple methods would capture more variants with confidence and allow a consensus call set to be generated. With continuous progress in technology and variant discovery, the SV database will become increasingly complete. Notably, variants called by multiple variant callers does not necessarily imply that they are true variants, as algorithms can be susceptible to the same biases. Thus, the validation of this consensus set will also be required. Additionally, merging the output will require agreements on the way variant callers operate (i.e. the definition of each SV subtype and quality measures), which would become standardised through further practice.

Genome evolution could be driven by the accumulation of SVs. For large insertions, new genes may be present. AUGUSTUS (Stanke et al., 2004) is a tool for gene prediction that could be applied to uncover specific genes in wild isolates. Furthermore, a closer assessment of the accumulated regions in genomes across the tree is needed. Noticeable enrichment for INDELS of a certain size at certain chromosomal regions can be an indication of interesting events such as transposition. For example, two deletion peaks of 1244 and 2337 bp were associated with Cemar1 and Tc3 transposable elements in CB4856, respectively (Vergara et al., 2014). A peak could be the result of a single event in an ancestor strain or the genomic locus being fragile, with many independent events having taken place at this mutation hotspot among different strains. RepeatMasker (Tarailo-Graovac and Chen, 2009) can annotate repetitive elements to trace the origin of SVs. Cristian followed up with investigations on potential transposon activity.

Inferring strain relatedness from the SV tree has provided a similar result to that from SNPs, though some differences exist. Nonetheless, the primary limitation of using SVs alone to study worm evolutionary relationships is that SV can appear as a result of events such as recombination and outcrossing between strains. To reliably study the evolutionary history of this species, whole-genome alignment across the population is ideal but challenging. In addition, the presented analysis procedure could be refined to incorporate geographical

information to study SV demography and understand how wild isolates adapt to the various environments they reside in.

III. Functional consequences of SVs

3.1 Introduction

The motivation for surveying structural differences among the genomes of wild *C. elegans* isolates is to determine their impacts on the annotated genomic features so that phenotypic differences can be inferred. Since the quality of called INDELS was promising (see Chapter II), the potential functional impacts of these variants can be determined by *in silico* prediction. Given the huge number and complexity of potential consequences, the prioritisation of impacted genes for further investigation should be achieved comprehensively, i.e. the relevance for human studies, existing biological information and previous studies for the impacted genes should be integrated and compared.

As mentioned in Chapter I, several known SVs exist at important loci. It is also prudent to assess the sensitivity of our long-read approach in detecting these verified variants. I did not overlap SV coordinates reported by these studies with our call sets since these studies used older versions of the reference genome that had different sequence coordinates to the one used here. Nonetheless, I can compare the consequences with these previous studies because the gene names are the same.

3.1.1 Variant effect prediction

The Ensembl Variant Effect Predictor (VEP) (McLaren et al., 2016) is an online tool for predicting the functional effects of genomic variants, which works by mapping the input coordinates with the genome annotation. Both SNVs and SVs can be assessed for their potential effects in coding genes and regulatory regions.

For SVs, VEP can only predict effects for insertion, deletion and duplication, while the impacts of inversions and translocations cannot be reliably inferred. VEP only takes variant type and variant coordinates as inputs and thus cannot interpret the size information of each variant (this length is measured differently from what can be inferred from the coordinates, as

the best reported start and stop does not necessarily agree with the best supported length). Consequently, overlapping features are defined based only on the input coordinate range and the variant type. This implies that the effects of an SV are calculated from a structural perspective and that the sequence composition of the affected locus is not taken into consideration. Thus, we cannot detect the events that lead to the creation of a transcription factor binding site or the insertion of a stop codon.

VEP requires the start and end position to be precise for accurate effect prediction. Sniffles reports the most strongly supported start and end points for a variant. For deletions, this is well represented since their breakpoints can be more easily defined (i.e. the size difference between the breakpoints is very close to the variant size). Meanwhile, this is not the case for insertions. This should generally be a focal point, i.e. the start and end positions should be at a certain point in the genome since sequences are inserted in a specific genomic locus. Sniffles outputs a large interval here for insertions (see examples in Table 2.3). (This also indicates that insertions are more complicated than deletions in terms of reporting the precise location.) Since the start and end coordinates of insertion cannot be precisely obtained by Sniffles, insertions should be excluded from this analysis. In addition, deletion is reported with high confidence based on the PCR validation rate (although not at the base pair resolution) and general performance of variant detection. I have focused this analysis on the consequences of deletions in the *C. elegans* genome.

VEP can specify the consequences and downstream effects of structural changes, which can be ranked based on their severity. For example, transcript ablation refers to the total deletion of the transcript and it has the highest impact among all consequence groups. Frameshift variants are another group of high impact. Missense variants have a moderate impact and start or stop retained variants are in the low impact group. This categorisation facilitates the prioritisation of variants at the functional consequence level. OverlapBP (Overlap Base Pair) and OverlapPC (Overlap PerCentage) are two parameters calculated by VEP to represent the number of overlapping base pairs of a variant with a genomic feature and the percentage of the total transcript length affected. For transcript ablation, overlapPC is 100% by definition.

By default, both the 5' and 3' ends of the transcription start and end sites of each gene are extended by 5000 bp to analyse potential regulatory regions. These variants are assigned by VEP as 5' upstream or 3' downstream gene variant consequences. The 5' and 3' ends of this distance can be modified to better fit the worm model. These predictions are made for studies on the regulatory differences among wild strains.

3.1.2 Additional information

Once again, it is important to highlight the use of *C. elegans* as an essential model organism for developmental and pathological studies. Variants from homologous genes are valuable since mutations in a homologous gene are likely to have effects at the same residue in the gene of interest. Thus, existing knowledge on worms as well as human-relevant information can be used in the evaluation of the predicted downstream effects of reliable SVs. Moreover, information across different *C. elegans* resources can be compared to aid in understanding associated features.

Notably, RNA interference can silence targeted worm genes by feeding bacteria producing the dsRNA. This represents a forward genetics screening tool for inducing phenotypes and for functional genetic analysis/studying gene function. The *C. elegans* RNAi collection is a worm-specific RNAi feeding library designed for genome-wide loss-of-function studies. This reverse genetics library now targets 87% of currently annotated genes (<https://www.sourcebioscience.com/products/life-sciences-research/clones/rnai-resources/c-elegans-rnai-collection-ahringier/>). RNAi clone information permits cross-referencing between RNAi clones and natural knockout of the same gene.

SimpleMine is one of the web-based tool publically available on WormBase (<https://www.wormbase.org/tools/mine/simplemine.cgi>) that allows a multitude of gene data to be queried by mapping with WormBase gene IDs. A complete output has 29 columns providing information at the transcript, gene, protein, regulatory, interaction, expression location and functional study levels.

BioMart (Durinck et al., 2009) is a data mining tool that facilitates access to a large collection of biological databases. It is highly customisable and *C. elegans* Ensembl gene database can be loaded in search of entrez gene id, coding sequence length, and the number of transcripts, among other items. Since the *H. sapiens* Ensembl gene database can also be fetched in BioMart, the getLDS (get Linked DataSet) function of the BioMart R package can link these two BioMart datasets to provide homology information among these two species.

Another online tool known as OrthoList 2 (OL2) can search for orthologs specifically among worms and humans using gene identifier mappings (Kim et al., 2018). OL2 can take a WormBase ID, common name or locus ID as the input and provide information on the Ahringer RNAi clone library, Ensembl ID, HGNC symbol, number of supporting orthology prediction programs, protein domain prediction databases (InterPro and SMART) and a human disease association database (Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man (OMIM)). OL2 updated its previous release, OrthoList (Shaye and Greenwald, 2011), since changes were made to gene predictions in both the worm and human genome and because the orthology prediction methods have been updated. OL2 also compares and merges genes found by different programs. The present study also stated that the absence of a previously recognised homolog in this list should not be the only consideration when studying homology for the gene of interest. Consequently, information on orthologous genes from WormBase and Ensembl (via BioMart) should be obtained for comparison with this list.

Several resources can be used in estimating the clinical relevance of each human ortholog gene. Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) (Rogers, 1963) IDs are employed by the National Library of Medicine to specify the vocabulary used in indexing articles for the PubMed database. OMIM (McKusick, 1998) is an online catalogue of human genetic disorders. A gene with disease-relevant information has a specific 6-digit OMIM ID on the OMIM website. If a variant affects a gene with MeSH and/or OMIM IDs, this gene has implications for human disorders and could be highlighted as a potential disease model in *C. elegans*.

3.1.3 Functional enrichment

Functional enrichment analysis maps an input gene list to existing functional pathways and searches for the statistical overrepresentation of gene hits. Notably, g:Profiler (Reimand et al., 2016) is a tool commonly used in functional profiling for a multitude of model organisms, which includes *C. elegans* information from WormBase ParaSite (another portal for interrogating helminth genomics (Howe et al., 2017)). The gGOST function of g:Profiler can enrich the input in a range of known functional information sources, including MF (molecular function), BP (biological process), CC (cellular component), biological pathways, human diseases phenotypes, miRNA targets and regulatory targets, among others. WormMine also has a ‘gene set enrichment’ (GSE) tool that can search for overrepresented terms using ontologies from TEA (tissue), PEA (phenotype) and GEA (gene ontology) (Angeles-Albores et al., 2016).

3.2 Methods and Materials and Materials

3.2.1 VEP

VEP normally runs with an established genome in its database. In addition, the use of its ‘cache’ containing all transcript models, regulatory features and variant data for a specific species is recommended by VEP as the most efficient method for variant interpretation. However, since we have run variant calling with the new VC2010 reference assembly, I had to run VEP in a Docker virtualised container (ensemblorg/ensembl-vep, available on DockerHub). The VEP Docker image uses ubuntu:18.04 as the base image. I used the following command: “docker run -t -i -v ensemblorg/ensembl-vep --biotype -i input.vcf -o --custom input.annotation VC2010,gtf -fasta input.fasta” while Docker desktop was running. I used ‘biotype’ to add impacted regulatory features for each transcript to specify the consequences and severity of SVs. This allowed me to subset, for example, transcript ablation and frameshift variants for the subsequent analysis of variants at various impact levels. In addition to the output vcf file, a web page is generated that summarises the general statistics and consequences for each strain.

The annotation file for the VC2010 reference genome was shared by our collaborator (Yoshimura et al., 2019). This annotation was lifted over from N2 (genebuild-version WS264) to the VC2010 assembly. I adapted this file into a general feature format (GEF) that can then be interpreted by VEP. This annotation file is missing less than 2% of N2 genes. These include 214 coding genes and 530 ncRNA-coding genes that failed to be transferred from the N2 annotation. Since the annotated feature of the reference genome was given per transcript in this study, variant interpretation was performed at the transcript level and collapsed down to summarise the affected genes.

Since precise breakpoints are required by VEP, the VEP input files were filtered to ensure proper overlap with annotated features. By default, Sniffles assigned each variant a PRECISE or IMPRECISE tag based on a consensus of the breakpoints of the variants, i.e. if the standard deviation of both breakpoints is < 5 bp, the variant is marked as precise. I did not use this tag in PCR stratification because it is qualitative; instead, I used the standard deviation values of start and stop breakpoint to measure their accuracy, which are quantitative and can be ranked. Since precision is determined by the agreement of the reads, I retained the PRECISE filtered deletion calls. I ran VEP on these callsets to provide reliable predictions on the consequences of deletion events. I also generated VEP outputs for raw Sniffles deletions for overlapping our results with those of previous studies.

Regarding impact prediction for frameshift deletions, I selected filtered deletions with 0 s.d. start and end breakpoint. This is because frameshifts, by definition, change how codon triplets are read and disrupt the reading frame. Ensuring a shift in the reading frame requires inputs with 100% accurate coordinates. This filtered set of variants have a defined location in the genome. Therefore, changes in codons can be reliably inferred with accurate effect prediction.

3.2.2 Adding information to impacted transcripts

3.2.2.1 Biological information of annotated features

The SimpleMine master list for this study was downloaded from <https://www.wormbase.org/tools/mine/simplemine.cgi> with all impacted transcript feature names as the input. This list includes information on: WormBase status (whether this gene is

live/valid or dead and merged into other genes), sequence name, other name, operon, WormPep (predicted proteins from the *C. elegans* genome sequencing project), UniProt (protein information), TreeFam (database of animal gene trees), RefSeq (NCBI Reference Sequence database) mRNA and protein information, RNAi phenotypes observed, allele phenotype observed, sequenced allele names, interacting genes, expression patterns in tissue, expression pattern and tissue localisation associated with life stages, life stages and tissue involved in genomic studies, disease information, human orthologs, summarised expression clusters, references (all the PubMed ID (pmid) for the relevant WormBase paper), concise descriptions and automated descriptions summarised by WormBase. Notably, not all of these pieces of information are useful in studying SV-impacted genes; therefore, I selected more useful information for a few important case studies below.

The 'celegans_gene_ensembl' database was gathered via BioMart 2.41.7, from which I obtained the following attributes: 'External_gene_name', 'ensembl_gene_id', 'wormbase_transcript', 'transcript_count', 'transcript_length' and 'cds_length'.

I overlapped the VEP output with information on WormBase (SimpleMine) and Ensembl (BioMart) based on the transcript feature names. Information from both sources are needed; for example, I added the number of transcripts from BioMart and the transcript name from SimpleMine for all impacted entries. This allows observations on the overall effects of a gene, i.e. if all transcripts have been affected or residual transcripts can complement the affected ones.

Reported case studies are selected by manual inspection of their consequence severity (overlapPC can be regarded as one of the calculated variant consequences), the presence of human ortholog and popularity of human studies, RNAi phenotypes, number of strains with the impact and number of transcripts affected.

3.2.2.2 Human homologs and clinical relevance

To determine if a gene of interest in *C. elegans* has an ortholog in humans, I compared the information provided by WormBase using Ensembl with the entire hit list of the OL2 legacy gene dataset. I downloaded the OL2 list from its website (<http://ortholist.shaye-lab.org>). For

candidates that were highly likely to have a human homolog, I added clinically relevant OMIM and MeSH terms according to the human gene ID of the impacted gene of interest in the table. The resource PubTator <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/CBBresearch/Lu/Demo/PubTator/> provides indexes cataloguing all gene names and diseases mentioned in PubMed abstracts. From this database of “tagged” PubMed abstracts, my supervisor, Martin Hemberg, gathered MeSH IDs for all gene names mentioned with a disease in the same abstract. He also included the number of citations for each publication with a co-mentioned gene and disease and supplied me with a list of disease names to map the MeSH IDs (manuscript in preparation).

3.2.2.3 Overlaps with previous studies

Supplementary data from previous studies (Maydan et al., 2007), (Maydan et al., 2010), (Vergara et al., 2014) were used in overlapping with our Hawaiian (CB4856) deletions based on transcript name. I used a hypergeometric test to calculate the probability of obtaining the number of overlaps or more among our gene list and Vergara et al. (2014) list, via `phyper` in R (`phyper = (q-1,m,n,k, lower.tail = FALSE)` q = number of overlaps, m = number of their hits, n = total number of genes (according to the paper = 21303, assumed here this is the same in our list), k = number of our hits).

3.2.2.4 Functional enrichment

Since the present study involves 21 strains, the manual entry of individual files into web-based tools is not ideal. Therefore, I used R package `gprofiler2` 0.1.5 to perform a functional enrichment analysis for each strain in RStudio. I also attempted using the R package `InterMineR` for running WormMine (WormBase) gene set enrichment, which did not work with my list due to it being too long. This R tool from WormMine is new and this problem has not yet been solved. Thus, for certain strains, I used the online tool <https://wormbase.org/tools/enrichment/tea/tea.cgi> to perform GSE of deletions to compare the output of GSE and `gprofiler2`.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 VEP output

From the filtered precise set, I used deletions of 50 bp-10 kbp as the VEP input. All overlapping deletions and transcripts with annotated features were processed by VEP. The number of filtered precise deletions involved in variant predictions was 31,842. The total number of consequences returned was 236,014 for all 21 strains. These reported consequences collapse down to 39,661 transcripts and 31,085 genes (309,09 for common gene names). Important genomic features affected by SVs include 5,545 coding variants, 1,587 ablated transcripts, 38,472 intron variants, 209 in-frame deletions, 3,015 5' UTR variants, 3,627 3' UTR variants, 37 start retained variants, 2,882 stops lost and 37 starts lost. The vast majority (229,806/236,014; 97.4%) of consequences are modifiers, while 207 are moderate and 5,048 are of high impact. The majority of consequences include 93,547 upstream variants and 94,962 downstream variants, which implies that the 5000 bp range between a variant and a transcript, which was used by default for predicting these effects, is too wide. Ideally, this distance should be set such that it is unlikely that there are any other genes in this interval. Overall, 20.6% (48,673/236,014) of the hits have human homolog genes (based on OL2), which collapses down to 3,070 genes and 932 with OMIM phenotypes.

Typically, there are multiple consequences for each SV. This could be the result of the variant length since long SVs are more likely to affect several important loci; or the presence of multiple isoforms at a particular locus. To illustrate this, the most frequently affected gene from the hit list is *pqn-80*, which was reported 1,419 times. Several factors contribute to this result. Firstly, SVs are found at this gene locus for 13 strain wild isolates. Secondly, this gene, which encodes a glutamine (Q)- asparagine (N)-rich ('prion') domain, has the largest number of transcript isoforms among all worm genes. A total of 51 transcripts exist within this genomic region (see Figure 3.1). Thirdly, this genomic locus is shown here as being very polymorphic, with multiple SVs affecting the same gene. QX1791 has the largest number (216) of predicted effects among all strains, of which, the transcript Y111B2A.14a.1 has been

reported 5 times in this strain (Figure 3.2). I also checked the IGV evidence for these frequent deletions within this region (Figure 3.3). (Based on alignment visualisation, ID 4 only reported the end of the real variant. There is a variant before ID 3 reported, though it was filtered out since the two variants are very close and had a similar length, resulting in filtering not being effective.) Moreover, deletions here are close, with each deletion affecting a different area and proportion of the same transcript, as shown by the percentage overlapping (OverlapPC). In summary, five deletions were discovered on one of the transcripts of *pqn-80* in this particular strain. A breakdown of all 1,419 hits of *pqn-80* can be seen in Figure 3.4. As transcript length becomes shorter going down the list (Figure 3.1), the counts of predicted effect drop (i.e. fewer variants are hitting a small region).

Figure 3.1: A screenshot of the genome browser preview of *pqn-80* (Y111B2A.14) on WormBase. There are in total 51 transcripts or isoforms of this gene. The length of the transcript goes down as descending the list, since less exons are retained.

	Location	Allele	Feature	Strain	OverlapBP	OverlapPC
1	chrIII:12932199-12932253	deletion	Y111B2A.14a.1	QX1791	55	0.23
2	chrIII:12935777-12936492	deletion	Y111B2A.14a.1	QX1791	716	2.96
3	chrIII:12942039-12942233	deletion	Y111B2A.14a.1	QX1791	195	0.81
4	chrIII:12951138-12951195	deletion	Y111B2A.14a.1	QX1791	58	0.24
5	chrIII:12954674-12954978	deletion	Y111B2A.14a.1	QX1791	305	1.26

Figure 3.2: The reported consequence of Y111B2A.14a.1 in QX1791.

Figure 3.3: An IGV browser snapshot (chromosome III: 12,931,000-12,956,600) of alignment evidence for six deletions affecting Y111B2A.14a.1 in strain QX1791. Green arrows point to deletions reported by Sniffles. The alignment bam file of long reads is mapped to the VC2010 assembly. Bottom track is the VC2010 annotation file. Pink and blue reads are aligned to the forward and reverse strand respectively. Mismatched positions are coloured in the coverage track. Deletions are represented by black lines in the reads. Insertions are represented by purple blocks/points in the reads.

Figure 3.4: Impact counts of each transcript of *pqn-80* for 13 strains. Each strain is represented by a panel. Transcript ID 1:51 on the x-axis is artificial and follows the order in (Figure 3.1) for 13 panels.

Each transcript of a gene can be affected multiple times and different strains are affected by different deletions. In aggregate, a large number of hits is generated. Again, some consequences are shared by multiple strains and some are private. Ideally, I could collapse this down for each transcript; however, there are slight differences in the deletion length among individual strains sharing this variant. Despite this being a detailed list, it reveals the issue of how VEP reports the variants without the systematic integration of all consequences for a gene. An overall impact of the gene must be estimated by the manual selection of all impacted transcripts.

However, there is a chance that Sniffles can call an incorrect SV, resulting in VEP will making incorrect predictions. Thus, it is recommended to check the genomic alignment of a variant in IGV and experimentally validate it before fully trusting their predicted impacts. One example of an impact on *gfi-3* due to transcript (M153.4) ablation is widespread among 17 strains and is also highly pathologically relevant (ANAPC5, MeSH:D00942). However, read alignments in IGV question the presence of this deletion. Therefore, experimental

validation of this variant and an investigation of potential secondary alignments are necessary.

Figure 3.5: An IGV snapshot (chromosome X: 14,820,330-14,832,482) of read alignments for the predicted transcription ablation of *gfi-3* in strain CB4856 (only one strain is shown here but the pattern is true across 17 strains). The reference genome is the VC2010 assembly. Bottom track is the VC2010 annotation file. Pink and blue reads are aligned to the forward and reverse strand respectively. Mismatched positions are coloured in the coverage track. Insertions are represented by purple blocks/points in the reads.

3.3.2 Predicted effects with additional information

To estimate the relevance of gene hits for genetic analysis and to prioritise affected genes of greater importance, I collected worm-relevant information from multiple worm repositories, human homology databases and potential disease associations. These pieces of information are included in the results to facilitate manual inspection of the predicted consequences (see Appendix 5: Examples of severely impacted transcripts with implications for human studies).

Among the hits, I manually curated a collection of genes that were associated with human diseases according to Ortholist2. I also summed the citations of studies on MeSH annotated

genes as a rough measure of the popularity of a gene in medical research. This information is used in the case studies below. For example, F42A6.5 has the largest number (16269) of citations, which implies that the human homolog gene *BRCA1* has been researched by a relatively larger number of studies. This gene is not yet studied in *C. elegans*, and it can potentially contribute to work on ovarian cancer. However, this may not be the case—see case study F42A6.5, below.

3.3.3 Previously discovered SVs

As previously mentioned, a few SVs that have been studied in the literature can be regarded as ‘positive controls’ to validate our variant discovery approach. I have also run VEP for raw deletions in case a previously studied gene was missing from the filtered set but was called by Sniffles. Given the potential issue of breakpoint determination, this facilitates the sensitivity assessment of Sniffles. Thus, I have compared the variants discovered here with previous studies.

3.3.3.1 Compare with previous CB4856 studies

The first aCGH study on Hawaiian genomic variation identified 570 impacted genes (Jones et al., 2007), among which 102 overlapped with our datasets. Moreover, in a study of copy number variation in 12 natural isolates of *C. elegans* (Maydan et al., 2010), the CB4856 subset had 338 variants longer than 10 kbp (median length of all deletions = 12084 bp), which may be excluded from analysis here. For the remaining 285 variants, 97 were recalled in our results. For variants that were not identified via aCGH, there could be probing problems such as bias in hybridisation. For variants that were detected only by aCGH and missed in our analysis, this could be due to size exclusion or miscalling by Sniffles. The Illumina and Roche sequencing study of genome-wide SV discovery in CB4856 (Vergara et al., 2014) reported 1,067 genes that were impacted by 1,430 deletions (median size = 85 bp, range from 4 bp-62,795 bp; no size selection here, as sizes were not reported in the list), from which 261 overlapped with our list. Overall, the Sniffles calls discovered here overlap with previously reported deletions to some degree. Sniffles identified deletions affecting 2,303 genes in CB4856, which is the largest set among all studies. Although the overlap between the two tools is modest, the number of affected genes is significantly larger than expected by chance ($p\text{-value} < 1e\text{-}16$, hypergeometric test).

3.3.3.2 *glb-5*

Variation in globin-5 (*glb-5*) has been shown to confer different sensory responses to hypoxia among wild strains of *C. elegans* (McGrath et al., 2009; Persson et al., 2009). The dynamic range of oxygen-sensing neurons can be tuned in Hawaiian (CB4856)-like wild isolates by GLB-5, but this is defective in the N2 reference. One of the studies (Persson et al., 2009) genotyped this locus in 98 wild strains, 6 of which are in our strain collection. Our analysis supports the results of all overlapping strains (AB1, CB4855, CB4856, MY23 and PB306) displaying the Hawaiian type deletion, which is distinct from N2. All our wild strain collections, except N2, belong to the Hawaiian-like group with a deletion at chromosome V: 5560114-5561163 (Figure 3.6, median size = 761 bp). As evident from the read alignments presented in Figure 3.7, this variant has imprecise breakpoints and has been filtered out from the raw variant data. For the two transcripts for this gene, the deletion at C18C4.1b is captured as a coding sequence variant and the deletion just upstream of C18C4.1d is captured as an intron variant.

Since all alignments were made using the VC2010/N2 reference genome, the actual duplication event in N2 makes this structural change appear as a deletion in wild isolates. This also adds to the importance of updating the reference genome and studying the recent adaptation of the reference N2 strain in a laboratory environment.

Ten years after the first analysis of structural changes for this gene, a systematic search of causal changes in genomic loci for phenotypic variation has become possible. While the wild isolates were genotyped by PCR in previous studies, the presence of an exon deletion in the wild isolates can now be confirmed with long-read sequencing.

Figure 3.6: IGV snapshot of coverage tracks of long-read alignments for 21 strains. This deletion in *glb-5* is observed in all wild strains except N2. Coverage tracks of read alignments are shown in order to accommodate tracks for all strains. Blank regions represent no coverage, in other words, deletions. All strains are shown, in the order: JT11398, AB1, CB4856, JU751, QX1211, PB306, LKC34, EG4725, JU775, PS2025, EG4946, CX11262, ECA248, DL200, ECA36, DL238, GXW1, QX1791, MY23, JU394, N2. Reference genome is the VC2010 assembly. Bottom track is the VC2010 annotation file. Mismatched positions are highlighted in the coverage tracks.

Figure 3.7: IGV evidence (chromosome V: 5,558,976-5,562,538) of *glb-5* exon deletion in strain CB4856. The read alignment track of long reads against the VC2010 reference genome is expanded and partially shown (to give examples of the size of this deletion). Deletions are shown by black lines in the reads annotated with size. Insertions are shown by purple blocks annotated with size. The annotation track indicates the gene construction of *glb-5*. Mismatched positions are coloured in the coverage track.

3.3.3.3 *plg-1*

Disruption of the *plg-1* gene by the insertion of *Cer1* (an LTR-retrotransposon) was observed in N2 (Palopoli et al., 2008). Males of strains with this insertion cannot deposit a copulatory plug after mating; thus, they are unable to prevent mating by other males. This study observed a global distribution of this loss-of-function allele in 48 strains that cannot complement N2 and 105 strains without the insertion that can still complement N2. Since the insertion is present in N2, this variation is identified as deletions in other isolates.

Our results agree with the deletion in CB4856 and the absence of the deletion in AB1. Impacts on the transcript F44E2.11 were predicted from deletions detected in 16 strains in our list, which excludes N2, JU394, JT11398, AB1 and EG4946 (from the phylogenetic tree in Figure 2.25, these are the most N2-related strains among our worm collection). All deletions were reported with a precise location on chromosome III (9115706-9124574), and a size of 8868 (except 8869 for DL238 and PB306). Alignments of the Hawaiian strain can be seen in Figure 3.8. I also checked the IGV evidence of all other strains. Interestingly, there are secondary alignments over this region for some strains, which could imply that *Cer1* is also present elsewhere.

Palopoli et al. (2008) also investigated the presence of *Cer1* and LTRs (long terminal repeats) elsewhere, which were found in MY23, PB306, PS2025 and ECA248. This agrees with the observations I have made in the present study, which suggest that although these deletions are verified in Sniffles, there are secondary alignments shown in IGV (Figure 3.8) for these four strains. In fact, these aligned reads also align at chromosomes V and II, which can be investigated further. CB4856 has intact *plg-1*, i.e. no insertion and no other *Cer1* is shown by the absence of alignments (highlighted in green in Figure 3.8).

Furthermore, there are no *Cer1* and LTRs elsewhere in N2 and AB1, which has *Cer1* in *plg-1*. Therefore, no secondary alignments can be observed for these two strains (Figure 3.9). There are also secondary alignments for other N2-like strains identified in our study (JU394, JT11398 and EG4946). Notably, there are unique alignments in addition to secondary alignments. This differs in the four strains in the middle of Figure 3.8, where only secondary alignments are found (breakpoints are indicated by arrows). For all N2-like strains with inserted sequences shown in Figure 3.9, there are also additional alignments from elsewhere in addition to the inserted sequences.

Figure 3.8: IGV evidence (chromosome III: 9,110,830-9,131,003) of deletion at F44E2.11 among 6 strains. The region highlighted in green is the reported 9 kb deletion in CB4856. The coverage and alignment tracks for CB4856, MY23, PB306, PS2025, ECA248 and QX1211 are shown in order. Reference genome is the VC2010 assembly. Bottom track is the VC2010 annotation file. Mismatched positions are highlighted in the coverage tracks. Deletions are represented by the absence of alignments or black lines in the reads (However, there are secondary alignments in the four strains in the middle). Insertions are represented by purple blocks/points in the reads. Pink and blue reads are aligned to the forward and reverse strand respectively. Blue arrows point to the breakpoints.

Figure 3.9: IGV evidence (chromosome III: 9,110,830-9,131,003) for N2 and N2-like strains with *CerI* insertion in F44E2.11 (*plg-1*). Read alignments and coverage tracks for N2, AB1, JU394, JT11398 and EG4946 are shown in order. Reference genome is the VC2010 assembly. Bottom track is the VC2010 annotation file. Mismatched positions are highlighted in the coverage tracks. Insertions are represented by purple blocks/points in the reads. Pink and blue reads are aligned to the forward and reverse strand respectively.

3.3.3.4 F42A6.5

A previous study on the Hawaiian strain CB4856 (Vergara et al., 2014) verified a ~2 kbp deletion in the F42A6.5 gene, which was considered a homolog to human *BRCA1* gene study. In our VEP output, this variant is precisely determined on chromosome IV: 3392987-3394981 (Figure 3.10) and its impact was classified as transcript ablation in 13 wild isolates. Although its presence has been cross-validated, the relevance of this structural variant for studying human genes must be revisited. In my result list, Ensembl has flagged

BRCA1 as a human homolog, while WormBase has flagged it as a predicted *BRCA1* C-terminal domain with no record of it being a human homolog. Moreover, it is not included in the OL2 master list. Although F24A6.5 shows homology to the human protein domain, BLAST (NCBI) searching its sequence will not give human *BRCA1* as a hit.

Figure 3.10: IGV evidence (chromosome IV: 3,392,421-3,395,904) for transcript ablation of F42A6.5 in strain CB4856. Long read alignments against the VC2010 reference genome are shown. Mismatched positions are highlighted in the coverage tracks. Genome annotation is shown at the bottom track. Deletions are represented by black lines in the reads and by the absence of coverage.

When I was searching SVs leading to high impacts on transcripts within the ablated group, two other genes follow the same story: transcript C31C9.6 is absent in 12 strains and OL2 does not agree with Ensembl on reporting it as an ortholog of human WASL (Wiskott-Aldrich Syndrome Like) gene; transcript Y46C8AL.1.1 (also known as *lec-73*), is deleted in one strain and is not orthologous to the human ABRA (Actin Binding Rho Activating) gene. Thus, these worm genes may not be useful for investigating human pathology with *C. elegans* as the model.

3.3.4 Case studies

From the curated list, I have highlighted the following case studies, which may provide a starting point for future functional validations and can thus be prioritised. Nevertheless, there remains a need to perform PCR and Sanger sequencing to confirm their presence. I have used IGV evidence again to evaluate the prediction.

3.3.4.1 *cbp-2*

Notably, *cbp-2* has been completely affected by a deletion on chromosome III (10192119-10201100) in strain LKC34 (ECA248 and GXW1 also based on the raw data, see figure 3.11). This gene has five transcripts, of which four (K03H1.10.1-4) are lost as transcript ablation, while K03H1.10.5 had 76.26% of its sequence deleted (Figure 3.11). Both Ensembl and OL2 reported *cbp-2* as an ortholog of CREB-binding protein (CREBBP/CBP) and WormBase flags human E1A binding protein p300 as its closely related paralog; therefore, *cbp-2* is predicted to have histone acetyltransferase, transcription coregulator, and zinc ion binding activity. A total of 20 MeSH items have been studied with CREBBP (a total of 287 citations) and the disruption of one copy of CBP in humans leads to a developmental disorder, Rubinstein-Taybi syndrome 1 (OMIM: 180849) (Kalkhoven et al., 2003), and it is also implicated in colorectal cancer. CBP and p300 are also important in immediate/early transcriptional responses, e.g. in response to neuronal activity (Flavell and Greenberg, 2008). Moreover, *cbp-2* has high sequence homology to *cbp-1*, which is also a CBP/p300 ortholog and has been studied extensively. *cbp-1* is involved in specifying multiple differentiation pathways of *C. elegans* (Shi and Mello, 1998) and positive regulation of apoptosis, thus antagonising Ras function and vulval induction (Eastburn and Han, 2005). Additionally, *cbp-3* is another CREBBP/p300 homolog. A range of RNAi phenotypes has been observed in *cbp-1* and *cbp-3*, but has strangely been recorded on WormBase as also being observed in *cbp-2* (*cbp-2* is 88.5% length of *cbp-1* isoform a and *cbp-3* is 73.9% length of *cbp-2*, given by WormBase). However, *cbp-2* remains poorly studied, and only one study has reported it as a chromatin modifier (Ho et al., 2015). The transcript ablation observed for *cbp-2* in these strains is interesting, as this gene may serve a role in worm development and its homolog has been implicated in human diseases. (No variant of *cbp-1* is found; immediately downstream

of *cbp-3*, there is a deletion and thus an impact has been predicted for *cbp-3*. Whether these genes are functional and could complement *cbp-2* function requires further investigation.)

Figure 3.11: IGV evidence (chromosome III: 10,186,493-10,206,725) for *cbp-2* deletion in strain LKC34 and GXW1, indicated by the black arrow. Read alignments of N2 are shown above the track for LKC34 for comparison. ECA248 was also predicted for by Sniffles, the alignment evidence here indicates potential secondary alignments. Reference genome is the VC2010 assembly. Mismatched positions are highlighted in the coverage tracks. Deletions are represented by the absence of read alignments (blank regions). Insertions are represented by purple blocks/points in the reads. Bottom track is the VC2010 annotation file.

3.3.4.2 *cst-2*

Protein-coding transcript C24A8.4 is fully deleted in two strains based on the filtered list, namely ECA36 and MY23 (in fact, seven strains based on the raw data, but five are filtered

out, including DL238, QX1211, QX1791, CB4856 and DL200). The deleted region is on chromosome X: 4499927-4508339, and the transcript is ablated with OverlapBP = 2885, OverlapPC = 100. This transcript encodes Caenorhabditis STE20-like kinase and only one transcript (C24A8.4.1) exists for this gene. This gene product is predicted to have ATP-binding activity and protein kinase activity. It is commonly known as *cst-2* or tag-306. Moreover, it is expressed in the AQR and PQR (neuronal classes) and there are six reference publications on WormBase. WormBase also reported the *Drosophila* ortholog Hippo and human ortholog gene STK3 (serine threonine kinase 3), which is also supported by OL2. This gene is associated with myeloproliferative syndrome (MeSH:C563551). All of the preceding information was extracted from the result list.

In addition to *cst-2*, *cst-1* is orthologous to STK3 and appears to regulate oxidative stress responses and the determination of lifespan. CST-1 functions upstream of the DAF-16/FOXO transcription factor and physically interacts with RSF-1, the *C. elegans* homolog of the Ras-association domain family protein 1 (from WormBase). This FOXO TF regulates many phenotypes associated with Insulin/IGF-1-like signalling pathways, such as metabolism and ageing (Brunet et al., 1999). It was shown that long-lived mitochondrial mutants of the worm require DAF-16 and DAF-16 interacting proteins, which includes *cst-1/2* (Senchuk et al., 2018). In fact, C24A8.4 is upstream of *cst-1* (F14H12.4), which can be seen at the bottom track of Figure 3.12. Since this deletion extends into the upstream region of *cst-1*, there are consequences recorded as modifiers of *cst-1* in the list. *cst-1* possibly remains functional in strains lacking *cst-2*. The transcriptional level of *cst-1* in *cst-2* mutant strains can be measured by RNA-seq. This gene could be duplicated in a worm ancestor and some strains may have lost one copy; or, on the contrary, this gene has been duplicated in some strains.

A wide range of phenotypes have been observed in experiments involving *cst-1/2* RNAi clone X-2J23, including body muscle dystrophy, body wall muscle sarcomere morphology variation, an increase in fat-associated bodies, a reduced frequency of body bend, head behaviour variation, reduced locomotion, variant locomotion variation, reduced pharyngeal pumping, shortened life span and sluggishness (Keating et al., 2003; Lehtinen et al., 2006). This gene is also enriched in ontologies including response to stimulus, cell communication, signalling and signal transduction. This may be a good candidate for studying the Hippo

pathway, which influences autophagy and apoptosis, among other variables (Wilkinson et al., 2015). One study also suggested *STK3* as a new target for a subset of acute myeloid leukaemia (Camgoz et al., 2018). Therefore, the nematode variant may attract many research interests.

Figure 3.12: IGV evidence (chromosome X: 4,496,074-4,512,192) for ablated *C24A8.4* (*cost-2*, black arrow) in ECA36 and MY23 and intact *C24A8.4* in GXW1. This is upstream of *F14H12.4a* (*cost-1*, blue arrow). Long read alignments track of GXW1, ECA36 and MY23 are shown in order. Read alignments of GXW1 demonstrate an absence of deletion for comparison. Reference genome is the VC2010 assembly. Mismatched positions are highlighted in the coverage tracks. Deletions are represented by the absence of read alignments (blank regions). Insertions are represented by purple blocks/points in the reads. Bottom track is the VC2010 annotation file. The other transcripts affected are *C24A8.6* (predicted to have G protein-coupled receptor activity) and *F14H12.10* (an ncRNA).

3.3.4.3 Frameshift: *cyp-33C6*

In addition to full deletion, another severe consequence of deletion is frameshift. A private deletion (ChrV:2296287-2296369) in strain ECA36 was predicted to cause a frameshift in the

coding sequence of the gene *cyp-33C6*, with impacts on both transcripts F41B5.7a.1 (1485bp) and F41B5.7b.1 (1383bp). This gene is predicted to have oxidoreductase activity and is an ortholog of human cytochrome P450 CYP2J2, which is implicated in lung cancer and other diseases. Although it is a potential candidate, the validity of frameshift needs to be revisited. Figures 3.13.a and 3.13.b present IGV screenshots of the reported variants. Breakpoints were reported as 0 since inconsistent reads were ignored. Most reads supported base T at both breakpoints (where the arrows are pointing), which may cause changes in the open reading frame, while other alignments at this locus suggest uncertainties regarding the exact locus. Frameshift variants are not reliably determined by Sniffles, as absolute breakpoints are challenging to obtain. Consequently, their predicted effects need to be treated with caution.

Figure 3.13.a: IGV evidence (chromosome V: 2,296,281-2,296,321) for frameshift deletion of *cyp-33C6* in strain ECA36. The start breakpoint of the variant (blue arrow) in long-read alignments against the reference genome VC2010 is shown. Deletions are represented by black lines in the reads. The sequence track indicates the nucleotide identity. The amino acid sequence and the genome annotation is shown at the bottom track.

Figure 3.13.b: IGV evidence (chromosome V: 2,296,350-2,296,375) for frameshift deletion of *cyp-33C6* in strain ECA36. The end breakpoint of the variant (blue arrow) in long-read alignments against the reference genome VC2010 is shown. Deletions are represented by black lines in the reads. Mismatched positions are shown in the reads and coloured in the coverage track. The sequence track indicates the nucleotide identity. Amino acid sequence and the genome annotation are shown at the bottom track.

3.3.5 Functional enrichment

Across the wild worm isolates, I summarised significantly enriched GO categories among the impacted genes that were reported by gprofiler2 (interface to the ‘g:Profiler’ toolset): the system process is enriched in the most impacted pathways among the majority of strains (11 strains); carbohydrate binding is enriched in 6 strains; cell communication is enriched in 5 strains; cellular response to hormone stimulus, cellular response to lipid, cellular response to organic cyclic compounds, cellular response to steroid hormone stimulus, signalling receptor activity, steroid hormone-mediated signalling pathway and transmembrane signalling receptor activity are enriched in 4 strains. Signal transduction gene families in CB4856 were previously reported as being prone to deletions (Maydan et al., 2007). Overall, this

observation may be general among the wild isolates based on the enrichment results presented here.

WormBase gene set enrichment results for CB4856 are presented in Figure 3.14. Compared to gprofiler2 results, overlaps exist among the two methods regarding GSE (Two ontologies: an intrinsic component of the membrane and membrane); however, gprofiler2 can also perform transcription factor enrichment (efl-1 and gei-11 reported for CB4856). Meanwhile, GSE can provide information on phenotypes and tissue enrichment. Notably, these two datasets could be integrated (first running GSE in R with batch inputs is required).

A:

B:

C:

Figure 3.14: A: Gene Ontology enrichment analysis results for CB4856, B: Phenotype enrichment analysis results for CB4856, C: tissue enrichment analysis results for CB4856. GO categories with $Q < 0.05$ were considered significantly enriched, classification consists of three domains: biological processes, cellular components and molecular functions. The y-axis shows the value of $-\log_{10}Q$ of the category, i.e. the GO term with the highest $-\log_{10}Q$ is determined the most significant enrichment.

3.4 Discussion

I used a bioinformatic approach to predict the functional impacts of SVs in *C. elegans* transcripts. Variant effect prediction is restricted by the quality of the variants, with only accurate deletions being studied here. This data recalled previously detected variants throughout the genomes of wild isolates, despite *glb-5* not being precisely determined here. Since VEP overlaps the coordinates with the annotated genome, this software can be rerun with insertions and duplications to determine the number of potentially affected loci, even though they cannot be annotated with confidence.

SV effect prediction by VEP is also currently restricted by the tool's functionality. Some SV types (e.g. inversions) remain to be investigated since VEP cannot interpret them. Variant size, especially for insertions, should be added as an input parameter. Moreover, the effects of co-occurring variants impacting the same gene should be integrated. Therefore, the capacity of VEP to analyse more complex variant types, to add variant quality information and to integrate consequence of local variants is yet to be developed.

Furthermore, certain VEP functions exist but are only available for a small range of model organisms; for example `--appris` can annotate alternatively spliced transcripts and automatically selects the principal transcript isoforms for each gene. Currently, this is only available for human, mouse, zebrafish, rat and pig (Rodriguez 2012), while VEP only has one for the human assembly. Since the relative importance of each transcript remains unclear in the present study, it remains difficult to estimate if a large deletion in a more lowly expressed transcript is more severe than a small deletion in a highly expressed transcript. The `--domains` option can add the names of overlapping protein domains to output (e.g. from Pfam), though it also cannot be applied here to provide domain information, due to the use of the VC2010 GTF file for annotation, which is not present in the VEP cache or Ensembl database.

Notably, alternative bioinformatic tools are available for effect prediction, such as Annovar (Wang et al., 2010) and Snpeff (Cingolani et al., 2012). These are similar to VEP since they

are SNV specific and their functionality for SVs remains to be improved. As such, improvements will be required due to the sharp increase in SV studies.

Since VEP relies heavily on the annotation of the reference genome, the quality of the annotation file should be high, while misinterpretation in transcript isoforms and annotation versions should be avoided. It is important to note that the VC2010 reference genome has had 98% of its annotations (still encoded unchanged products) lifted over from the N2 reference genome (Yoshimura et al., 2019). Some variants may have effects in untransferred or unannotated regions that have not been studied to date. It is also necessary to check updates in genome annotations to determine if new genes have been added or updated in gene names have occurred between releases. Ongoing improvements to the worm reference genome and its corresponding annotation file necessitate the recalling of variants and the reassessment of variant impact, which would facilitate improvements in variant effect estimation.

The list of deletions with predicted effects can serve as a resource for the molecular dissection of phenotypic variation among wild isolates, as well as for researchers who are interested in finding natural knockout strains and related RNAi clones. Additional information can be obtained from Ensembl, WormBase, OMIM, MeSH, TreeFam and InterPro for impacted genes. Although most candidates in the list do not have all of the necessary information available, some may have certain notable features, i.e. some have more relevance for human disease, or some have RNAi models with reduced viability. Strains overlapping human homologs can contribute towards *C. elegans* translational research for modelling diseases. Furthermore, abundant SVs in the genomes of the wild isolates highlight the importance of genetic background in functional studies. Genetic editing of a target gene could have different effects in different strains as there will be variation in components of the gene network.

There may be surprising cases where worms still tolerate dramatic defects in gene function and development. Thus, worm phenotypic plasticity is an area that remains to be explored. Further investigation of this list can focus on impacts in multigene families, i.e. if multiple members of a gene family are affected (Thompson et al., 2015; Vergara et al., 2014). I did not study impacts on gene families, although it is possible to identify rapidly evolving gene

families. My list also lacks information on the functional importance of each gene; in other words, if a gene is essential or accessory. Essential genes are indispensable for the growth and survival of a species, while accessory genes are required for survival under certain conditions; for example, with *glb-5* duplication in N2 disrupting gene function, phenotypic variation can only be observed when oxygen level varies. Therefore, changes in essential genes will bring a more severe outcome and should be prioritised for investigations.

Variants impact mostly the non-coding regions of the genome, which remain to be investigated. Overall, 79.9% of the total reported effects are upstream and downstream gene variants (5 kbp). Variants up or downstream of a gene may also serve a role in changing the regulatory landscape of the worm gene regulatory network. In addition, 5' and 3' untranslated regions can influence translation and associated variants have been reported. Genomic changes in regulatory regions should also include variation at specific loci, such as piRNA clusters. Although some variations have been observed among piRNAs, many variants that may have been missed as piRNAs are 21 nucleotides long, which is below the size of SVs defined here. Moreover, subsequent transcriptional changes should be validated. RNA-seq data can be gathered as direct readouts of the transcriptional activity, which also allows regulatory changes to be determined.

Representation of SV localisation can also be improved. Unlike IGV being used here as a desktop genome browser, one can visualise the variant with many annotated features at the same time when this data become public online. The JBrowse Genome Browser can be operated through a web browser and has been used as an online tool on WormBase (<https://wormbase.org/tools/genome/jbrowse-simple/>), with the WormBase reference assemblies being loaded alongside a variety of other information. Furthermore, Ribbon (Nattestad et al., 2016) is a specific tool for visualising structural variation and complex genome alignments.

Notably, I performed a limited analysis on the functional enrichment results. As such, more detailed analysis on these would be useful to highlight important genes that have contributed to the most affected pathways, GO terms, phenotypes, *etc.*

SVs mark the major differences between genomes, have profound downstream consequences and may underlie the apparent phenotypic variation among wild isolates. Systematic variant effect interpretation requires established information on worm genes, orthologous genes and the post-transcriptional regulation of gene expression. Deletion alone has generated a vast amount of information to be processed. With the additional assessment of other variant types, a more efficient method searching interesting hits is required.

Regarding future case studies of interest, the presence of a variant should be confirmed by PCR evidence or sequencing among strains that share the impacts. This would distinguish SVs *in vivo* or variant calling errors *in silico*. All analyses here are only predictions, while potential effects on phenotypes should be confirmed with functional genetics. Gene expression is an intermediate phenotype that can be measured. Moreover, there are targeted high-throughput methods for evaluating the functional effects. For example, chromatin immunoprecipitation coupled with next-generation sequencing can be used to read h3k27ac levels in *cbp-2* mutants, as the deletion of CBP/p300 in mammalian cells reduces histone H3K27 acetylation, which is required for enhancer activity (Jin et al., 2011; Raisner et al., 2018). ChIP-seq can also determine FOXO recruitments for the *cst-2* mutants. Kumar and Mukhopadhyay (2019) have generated FOXO-specific ChIP-seq protocols for *C. elegans*.

IV. Conclusion

In this long-read sequencing-based SV detection assay for wild isolates of a phenotypically divergent species, I compared SVs identified using split-read-based (Sniffles) and assembly-based (Assemblytics) approaches. Despite the finding that these two methods only agree on a subset of variants, variability in the number of SVs across the strains was consistent. Due to the lack of a sufficient number of previously verified SVs of each strain, validation of the variants was needed. I stratified Sniffles INDELS into two confidence groups according to variant quality and performed technical validation of the stratified variants across the population via PCR amplification and IGV visualisation of the long-read alignments. Validation results demonstrated more authentic deletion calling than insertion calling, but with overall high confidence for SV identification. Although I validated only a small set of SVs in this study, this set can serve as a useful ground-truth list for others attempting to develop and benchmark new variant callers in *C. elegans*. Future experiments could also validate other variant types, variants identified by other methods (Assemblytics or other methods) and variants selected as case studies.

In the present study, I examined evolutionary distance among the strains based on the coincidence of SVs among them, and the population structure derived from SV calls with the SNP call-based tree was also compared. Having gathered the first SV dataset of 21 wild strains, more unstudied strains should be investigated to determine if shared structural differences are due to an ancient origin shared by these strains or an innate change specific to the reference. Further investigations could also contribute to a clear and thorough understanding of nematode evolution.

Overall, SVs are less prevalent than SNVs in the divergent CB4856 *C. elegans* strain (Kim et al., 2019); however, the proportion of affected genomes that I calculated herein is much larger than that of the SNVs (only 0.2%). For humans, there are approximately 10 Mb of variation (>50 bp) in a typical individual compared to the human GRCH38 reference (Chaisson et al., 2019). Proportionally, this (~25,000 SVs per individual) is lower than the abundance of SVs in the *C. elegans* genome, considering the human genome is 30 times the

size of the nematode genome. Thus, the amount of sequence variation in wild *C. elegans* isolates is substantial.

I then predicted the downstream effects for the most accurately called group of variants (deletions in the genome), studied the consequences of different biotypes within this list and annotated them with alongside relevant biological information. Previously reported cases studies are well captured, and I have highlighted a few interesting examples for future functional studies. Some variants may contain weak alignment evidence; thus, one should check for the presence of the variant. Nonetheless, validation here is merely a rough estimate of the location and size of variants since PCR amplifies a large region covering the target; therefore, breakpoint precision cannot be inferred. In order to make meaningful calculations on the severity of impacts of SVs that overlap with features, high confidence at the start and end of an SV should be ensured, which is especially required by frameshift impact prediction. The use of Sanger sequencing for a putative genomic locus can provide more precise estimations.

This annotated SV database of *C. elegans* is a resource of natural knockout or knockdown genes in the wild isolates. As an important genetic model, the prioritisation of genes more relevant to human disease can assist research on modelling human diseases using *C. elegans*. However, the utility of this nematode SV dataset is not restricted to studies on development and human diseases, as it also empowers worm genome research aiming to track the ongoing diversification and adaptation of both the lab and wild strains. Verified structural variation can be integrated with phenotypic differences across the species to perform genome-wide association (GWA) mappings, as has been performed for rice (Fuentes et al., 2019). In fact, quantitative traits, such as hybrid incompatibility and copulatory plugging, were mapped with SNPs between N2 and CB4856 (Rockman and Kruglyak, 2009). CeNDR (<https://www.elegansvariation.org/>) can perform GWA mapping with SNPs in the database for a phenotype of interest in *C. elegans*, while SVs are additional groups of genotypic variation that can be added to this analysis.

The question of why wild nematodes lack essential genes or have dysfunctional copies and still manage to stay phenotypically healthy remains to be answered. There are several

possible explanations for this phenomenon: due to natural suppressors of these benign mutations or redundant genes complementing the gene or evolutionary innovation emerged with similar function. Although the rationale for cataloguing large genomic changes and their impacts is to characterise underlying changes that can account for phenotypic variation, it is inherently difficult to directly link an SV with a particular phenotype in the present work. A genotype can comprise several alleles and a phenotype can be multigene-encoded. Dominance and epistasis are interactions between alleles and between genes, respectively, which implies that complex genetic networks are undercharacterised. For instance, there could be a few polymorphic genes with major effects as well as many genes with minor effects to account for a trait. Whether genomic variation can translate into variations at the level of functionally important proteins requires further investigation. Post-transcriptional and epigenetic regulatory pathways can also serve a role in tuning gene expression without changes to DNA sequences. Thus, it remains necessary to integrate SVs with transcriptomic evidence.

The ‘missing heritability’ problem, where genetic variation cannot fully explain the heritability of traits, is well-known. The integration of multi-omics data is required to bridge the gaps and facilitate the improved mapping of genetic variants to phenotypes. Additional genomic data, such as SNV data, can be restudied with more complete genome assemblies. Transcriptome can provide functional readouts at the transcript level. The nematode phenomes are also available on Worm Phenotype Ontology to supply phenotypic evidence (Schindelman et al., 2011). Recently, the neural networks of both sexes of *C. elegans* have been mapped (Portman, 2019). Moreover, an increased focus on candidates modulating neuronal activities can aid the understanding of nematode behavioural variation. Metadata from this highly supportive infrastructure and wealth of online resources should be interpreted with SVs to gain an improved understanding of genomic events in nematode evolution and divergence.

In addition, the significance of our work is evident from a technological perspective. The strength of systematic variant detection via third generation sequencing and the corresponding long-read variant callers has been demonstrated by the high validation rate of the predicted variants. Comprehensive SV identification has not become practically possible

until the emergence of the third generation sequencing. This form of sequencing has revolutionised genome research and replaced second-generation sequencing technologies and microarrays as the leading platform for investigating complex genomic rearrangements at base-pair resolution.

However, tools and resources for SV studies have lagged behind. Based on the validation results, insertions are poorly characterised in comparison. A sensible tool for the local assembly of insertion reads is crucial to improve insertion calling confidence and thus downstream effect prediction. CrossStitch can compute a local assembly for a variant, using reads that support the presence of a variant reported by Sniffles (<https://github.com/schatzlab/crossstitch>). These reads can be extracted and assembled to provide a consensus sequence of the SV. I managed to run the tool until the local alignments stage but failed at outputting the assembled sequence. However, this tool will become easier to use and will allow the assessment of called insertions using different approaches. Variant effect prediction tools must enhance their power in order to study more complex structural consequences in general and at the domain level, as discussed in Chapter III.

A variety of new tools have recently emerged for structural variant calling from long-read data. For example, PBSV, which is also split-read-based, has recently been adopted in PacBio's SMRT Link GUI to support the SV calling workflow (<https://github.com/PacificBiosciences/pbsv>). SVIM is another long-read-based variant caller that analyses signatures in and between read alignments (Heller and Vingron, 2019). Oxford Nanopore can also sequence long reads, while a specific variant caller for Nanopore known as NanoSV (Cretu Stancu et al., 2017) may add another level of assessment to SV discovery. One Nanopore-based human sequencing project that ran Sniffles, PBSV, SVIM and NanoSV determined that although Sniffles is the most accurate, the use of other variant callers provides additional sensitivity and confidence (Coster et al., 2019). To obtain more accurate genome assemblies, HiC and BioNano optical mapping can be applied to improve assembly-based variant calling, thus allowing long-range DNA changes to be studied with confidence. Although there is a wide range of SV callers available, the number of callers that allow the detection of the entire spectra of SV at a low computational cost remains limited. The trade-off between cost and sensitivity should be considered for later projects.

In the future, sequencing technology may obtain increasingly longer DNA fragments to facilitate the elucidation of noisy genomic regions and one could approach a ‘complete’ worm genome. More population-scale SV studies will be performed running various variant detection algorithms by genomic research groups. Although SV callers have been extensively used in research to detect mutations, their potential use within routine clinical diagnostics remains limited. With reduced sequencing cost and computational burden, it should become possible for all individuals and SVs to be sequenced and catalogued.

In summary, a comprehensive database for validated and annotated SVs across *C. elegans* wild isotypes has yet to be gathered. Like many online repositories for sharing and accessing worm resources, this fine-resolution SV map will become publicly available. Human SVs were initially collected by the Database of Genomic Variants (<http://dgv.tcag.ca/>), which now represents only a subset of the SVs discovered by the 1000 genome project. It is likely that this nematode SV collection can be curated with community efforts to collect more strains and improve the quantity and quality of DNA changes in nematode isotypes. Through the ongoing curation of current knowledge, *C. elegans* is becoming an even more robust genetic tool to illuminate mechanisms relevant to human diseases.

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Appendices:

Appendix 1: Long read assemblies

The following metrics were collected by Cristian, which demonstrated that the genomes were sequenced deeply enough for variant discovery with Sniffles (based on the protocol) and *de novo* assemblies have reasonable sizes and the amount of contigs to apply Assemblytics (CX11262 is an outlier, but I still analyzed its Assemblytics output).

Parent strain	Total reads	Read length mean (bp)	Read length median (bp)	Coverage	Assembly size (Mb)	Number of Contigs
AB1	1295934	7976.03	5246	101	104.25	96
CB4856	2873207	7187.25	4891	202	104.37	90
CX11262	826602	8741.74	5392	71	95.28	405
DL200	1042359	11047.66	7986	113	103.86	65
DL238	2311701	10443.71	7092	237	105.22	82
ECA248	1421246	7314.82	6090	102	103.5	138
ECA36	1738843	7379.47	5216	126	105.24	137
EG4725	909777	6638.42	4065	59	102.52	135
EG4946	1388408	7035.76	5611	96	106.12	208
GXW1	2064529	12965.3	9595	262	105.49	85
JT11398	1790017	8144.08	6842	143	103.38	137
JU394	2039087	7046.43	5639	141	103.3	146
JU751	1094098	10488.79	6072	113	103.76	132
JU775	1142885	9978.56	7377	112	104.11	109
LKC34	1215816	8038.31	6698	96	102.99	123
MY23	837082	6669.77	5153.5	55	103.59	200
N2	847132	7055.08	5039	59	103.06	105
PB306	1507349	9139.64	7092	135	108.14	157
PS2025	2023244	6967.42	4628	138	103.57	94
QX1211	1165787	8898.36	5286	102	104.94	127
QX1791	2105178	13637.6	10201	281	106.44	66

Appendix 2: Length similarity

Length similarity of variants that are reported the two variant callers and are overlapping by coordinates, are calculated as Sniffles length / Assemblytics length.

75% similarity is an arbitrary threshold and most shared variants are within this range, while more divergent variants are not considered here

For example deletions (left) and insertions (right) in CB4856:

Appendix 3: Gel images

Gel images of the 32 amplified INDELs are shown below (ID 23.2 is the improved run of ID 23, with redesigned primers based on IGV evidence). For all gels, lane one is the ladder, lane two is N2 (the reference & control), lane three is the selected candidate that has been stratified into confidence groups. Identity number of each gel corresponds to the SV PCR candidate Table 2.2 & Table 2.3.

ID 1 Deletion

100 bp N2 CB4856 DL238 JU751 EG4725 LKC34 PB306 MY23 GXW1 JT11398 DL200 CX11262 QX1791 ECA36 QX1211 EG4946 JU394 AB1

ID 2 Deletion

100 bp N2 CB4856 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 JU394 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 EG4946 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1

ID 3 Deletion

1000 bp N2 CB4856 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 JU394 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 EG4946 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1

ID 4 Deletion

1000 bp N2 CB4856 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 JU394 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 EG4946 GXW1

ID 5 Deletion

100 bp N2 JU394 ECA36 QX1211 DL200 AB1 EG4725 CB4856 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 EG4946 PB306 QX1791 GXW1

ID 6 Deletion

100 bp N2 JU394 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 CB4856 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 EG4946 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1

ID 7 Deletion

100 bp N2 JU394 DL200 ECA36 CB4856 LKC34 QX1211 QX1791 GXW1 AB1 EG4725 JT11398 CX11262 DL238 JU751 MY23 EG4946 PB306

ID 8 Deletion

1000 bp N2 JU394 ECA36 MY23 QX1211 QX1791 GXW1 DL200 CB4856 LKC34 AB1 EG4725 JT11398 CX11262 DL238 JU751 EG4946 PB306

ID 9 Deletion

100 bp N2 MY23 DL200 EG4725 CB4856 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 EG4946 PB306 ABI ECA36 JU394 QX1211 QX1791 GXW1

ID 10 Deletion

100 bp N2 MY23 DL200 JU751 GXW1 ABI EG4725 ECA36 CB4856 JU394 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 EG4946 QX1211 PB306 QX1791

ID 11 Deletion

100bp N2 MY23 DL200 EG4725 CB4856 JU394 JU751 EG4946 QX1791 GXW1 ABI ECA36 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 QX1211 PB306

ID 12 Deletion

100 bp N2 MY23 DL200 EG4725 CB4856 JU394 JU751 EG4946 QX1791 GXW1 ABI ECA36 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 QX1211 PB306

ID 13 Deletion

100 bp N2 EG4946 AB1 EG4725 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 JU751 MY23 QX1791 GXW1 DL200 ECA36 CB4856 JU394 DL238 QX1211 PB306

ID 14 Deletion

100 bp N2 EG4946 EG4725 CX11262 LKC34 JU751 DL200 AB1 ECA36 CB4856 JU394 JT11398 DL238 MY23 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1

ID 15 Deletion

100 bp N2 EG4946 EG4725 CX11262 JU751 PB306 QX1791 DL200 AB1 ECA36 CB4856 JU394 JT11398 LKC34 DL238 MY23 QX1211 GXW1

ID 16 Deletion

1000 bp N2 EG4946 AB1 PB306 QX1791 DL200 EG4725 ECA36 CB4856 JU394 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 QX1211 GXW1

ID 17 Insertion

1000 bp N2 CB4856 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 JU394 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 EG4946 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1

ID 18 Insertion

100 bp N2 CB4856 DL200 EG4725 ECA36 JU394 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 EG4946 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 AB1 GXW1

ID 19 Insertion

1000 bp N2 CB4856 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 JU394 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 EG4946 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1

ID 20 Insertion

100 bp N2 CB4856 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 JU394 JT11398 EG4946 QX1211 GXW1 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 PB306 QX1791

ID 21 Insertion

1000 bp N2 JU394 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 CB4856 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 EG4946 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1 JT11398

ID 22 Insertion

100 bp N2 JU394 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 CB4856 JT11398 DL238 MY23 QX1211 QX1791 GXW1 DL200 CX11262 LKC34 JU751 EG4946 PB306

ID 23 Insertion & ID 23.2

100 bp N2 JU394 DL200 ECA36 CB4856 JT11398 LKC34 QX1211 QX1791 GXW1 AB1 EG4725 CX11262 DL238 JU751 MY23 EG4946 PB306

ID 24 Insertion

100 bp N2 JU394 DL200 ECA36 CB4856 JT11398 DL238 JU751 EG4946 QX1211 QX1791 GXW1 AB1 EG4725 CX11262 LKC34 MY23 PB306

ID 25 Insertion

100 bp N2 MY23 CB4856 CX11262 QX1211 QX1791 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 JU394 JT11398 LKC34 DL238 JU751 EG4946 PB306 GXW1

ID 26 Insertion

100 bp N2 MY23 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 JU751 EG4946 QX1211 QX1791 GXW1 DL200 CB4856 JU394 DL238 PB306

ID 27 Insertion

100 bp N2 MY23 JU751 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 CB4856 JU394 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 EG4946 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1

ID 28 Insertion

1000 bp N2 MY23 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 CB4856 JU394 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 EG4946 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1

ID 29 Insertion

1000 bp N2 EG4946 DL200 EG4725 CX11262 DL238 JU751 MY23 PB306 GXW1 AB1 ECA36 CB4856 JU394 JT11398 LKC34 QX1211 QX1791

ID 30 Insertion

1000 bp N2 EG4946 DL200 AB1 EG4725 ECA36 CB4856 JT11398 CX11262 LKC34 DL238 JU751 MY23 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1 JU394

ID 31 Insertion

100 bp N2 EG4946 AB1 CB4856 LKC34 JU751 QX1791 DL200 EG4725 ECA36 JU394 JT11398 CX11262 DL238 MY23 QX1211 PB306 GXW1

ID 32 Insertion

100 bp N2 EG4946 ECA36 JU394 JT11398 LKC34 DL238 DL200 AB1 EG4725 CB4856 CX11262 JU751 MY23 QX1211 PB306 QX1791 GXW1

Appendix 4: Regions that are likely to be unique to VC2010

9 variants are reported as common among 21 strains:

ID	Chromosome	SV type	Start	End	Length	Number of strains
1	I	Insertion	4531999	4532085	86	21
2	I	Insertion	9647173	9647430	255	21
3	II	Deletion	9365858	9366129	258	21
4	III	Deletion	10614840	10614970	95	21
5	III	Insertion	13197550	13197700	163	21
6	IV	Deletion	11763685	11763834	149	21
7	V	Deletion	1759939	1759973	630	21
8	V	Deletion	7919214	7919308	94	21
9	X	Insertion	3078344	3078459	110	21

Eight out of nine are likely to be true, based on the IGV evidence shown below for ID 1 to ID 9. For each variant, coverage tracks are shown here to accommodate tracks for 21 strains (in order: JT11398, AB1, CB4856, JU751, QX1211, PB306, LKC34, EG4725, JU775, PS2025, EG4946, CX11262, ECA248, DL200, ECA36, DL238, GXW1, QX1791, MY23, JU394 and N2). For ID 1 and ID 2, I also took examples from N2 and CB4856 to show the presence of the insertions; For ID 5, no variant is shown given coordinates reported by Sniffles, but I checked 20 bp upstream the range, an insertion may be present (evidence shown for JT11398, AB1, CB4856, and N2). These regions can be studied further to improve the VC2010 assembly.

ID 1: An insertion of 86 bp

ID 2: An insertion of 255 bp

ID 3: A deletion of 258 bp

ID 4: A deletion of 95 bp

ID 5: No insertion given the predicted location, but it may be present in this region.

ID 6: A deletion of 149 bp

ID 7: A deletion is predicted in this complex region, further investigation is required.

ID 8: A deletion of 94 bp

ID 9: A deletion of 110 bp

Appendix 5: Examples of severely impacted transcripts with implications for human studies

This is a part of the large list that have been selected from consequences predicted for filtered variants:

1. Variant has OL2 human ortholog
2. Variant has high impacts and overlapPC =100
3. There are MeSH and OMIM items reported

Only a few columns are shown here, Location: variant locus, Transcript: *C. elegans* transcript name, Gene: *C. elegans* gene name, Strain: *C. elegans* strain with the variant, Overlap: human gene name, Impact: sum of publications (comentioned MeSH IDs and gene names).

Location	Transcript	Gene	Strain	Overlap	Impact
chrV:3929920-3938573	B0213.12	cyp-34A7	ECA36	CYP2D6	505
chrV:3929920-3938573	B0213.12	cyp-34A7	QX1211	CYP2D6	505
chrV:3929923-3938573	B0213.12	cyp-34A7	QX1791	CYP2D6	505
chrV:2227091-2232229	C45H4.2	cyp-33C1	QX1791	CYP2C19	494
chrV:3913227-3921769	K07C6.2	cyp-35B3	QX1791	CYP2C19	494
chrV:3913227-3921769	K07C6.3	cyp-35B2	QX1791	CYP2C19	494
chrII:1560679-1569400	K05F6.11	poml-4	ECA248	PON1	176
chrII:1560679-1569400	K05F6.11	poml-4	PB306	PON1	176
chrII:1560679-1569401	K05F6.11	poml-4	QX1791	PON1	176
chrII:13781427-13788640	F37B1.5	gst-16	QX1211	GSTP1	113
chrII:15419574-15423675	Y53F4B.37	gst-32	DL238	GSTP1	113
chrV:2056729-2060799	F59A7.7	F59A7.7	DL200	SDS	102
chrV:2056729-2060799	F59A7.7	F59A7.7	EG4725	SDS	102
chrII:13990593-13994642	ZK131.6	his-12	EG4725	H2AFX	93
chrII:13992470-13999843	ZK131.6	his-12	QX1791	H2AFX	93
chrII:13992470-13996464	ZK131.6	his-12	QX1791	H2AFX	93

chrV:8933730-8934889	K06C4.3	his-21	PS2025	H2AFX	93
chrII:13992470-13999843	F08G2.2	his-43	QX1791	H2AFX	93
chrV:8933730-8934889	F07B7.10	his-51	PS2025	H2AFX	93
chrV:20232068-20236989	Y60A3A.18	skr-4	PB306	SKP1	26
chrV:18511449-18513775	Y37H2C.2	skr-6	PS2025	SKP1	26
chrV:18511449-18513775	Y37H2C.2	skr-6	CB4856	SKP1	26
chrIV:15558861-15564045	Y73F8A.17	tbx-40	QX1791	TBX22	25
chrX:4499927-4508339	C24A8.4	cst-2	ECA36	STK3	20
chrX:4499927-4508339	C24A8.4	cst-2	MY23	STK3	20